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Discovering Communities in Fine-Grained Temporal Interactions: A Modularity-Based Approach

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Abstract

Networks are everywhere: social networks, transportation systems, biological interactions. To make sense of them, researchers often look for *communities* — groups of elements that are more strongly connected to one another than to the rest of the network. But these networks constantly evolve over time, and the interactions they record come in different forms. Some happen in an instant, some extend over a period of time, others still carry a delay between their two endpoints. Besides, detecting communities that form, transform, and dissolve through such diverse data remains a challenge. It is one that existing methods typically address by transforming the data, slicing continuous time into snapshots and flattening interaction types, at the cost of discarding the very information the analysis aimed to capture.

This thesis proposes a new approach that identifies dynamic communities by pinpointing the exact moments when each member joins or leaves them, without any artificial time slicing. It relies on a new mathematical measure, *Longitudinal Modularity*, and an efficient algorithm to optimize it. Designed to preserve the data's original features — exact timing, weights, directions, multiple types of nodes, and the diverse temporal nature of interactions themselves — the framework avoids the destructive transformations that conventional methods require. Without claiming to cover every scenario, it is validated on data from social interactions, voting systems, urban mobility, and online social platforms. This opens new perspectives for analyzing the dynamics of complex systems.

Keywords: temporal networks, dynamic community detection, link streams, longitudinal modularity, continuous-time networks, complex networks.

Résumé

Les réseaux sont partout : réseaux sociaux, systèmes de transport, interactions biologiques. Pour les comprendre, on cherche souvent à y identifier des *communautés* — c'est-à-dire des groupes d'éléments fortement connectés entre eux. Mais ces réseaux évoluent au cours du temps, et les interactions qu'on y observe prennent des formes variées : certaines sont instantanées, d'autres ont une durée propre, d'autres encore introduisent un délai entre leur émission et leur réception. Détecter les communautés qui se forment, se transforment et se dissolvent à partir de données aussi variées reste un défi — que les méthodes existantes traitent généralement en transformant les données, en discrétisant le temps et en uniformisant les types d'interactions, au prix de l'information même que l'analyse cherche à saisir.

Cette thèse propose une nouvelle approche qui identifie des communautés dynamiques en déterminant précisément les instants où chaque membre les rejoint ou les quitte, sans aucun découpage temporel artificiel. Elle repose sur une nouvelle mesure mathématique, la *Modularité Longitudinale*, et sur un algorithme efficace pour l'optimiser. Conçue pour préserver les caractéristiques originales des données — instants exacts, poids, directions, hétérogénéité des nœuds, diversité temporelle des interactions — l'approche évite les transformations réductrices qu'imposent les méthodes conventionnelles. Si l'éventail des propriétés prises en charge ne prétend pas à l'exhaustivité, le traitement de chacune est éprouvé sur des données réelles issues d'interactions sociales, de systèmes de vote, de mobilité urbaine et de plateformes sociales en ligne, ouvrant de nouvelles perspectives pour l'analyse de la dynamique des systèmes complexes.

Mots-clés : réseaux temporels, détection de communautés dynamiques, flots de liens, modularité longitudinale, réseaux à temps continu, réseaux complexes.

Acknowledgements

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Declaration on the Use of AI Tools

During the preparation of this thesis, the author made use of generative artificial intelligence assistants (e.g. ChatGPT, Claude) as auxiliary writing and productivity aids. Their role included:

- suggesting potentially relevant references, each of which was subsequently retrieved, read, and critically assessed by the author before being cited.
- assisting with \LaTeX formatting and with the debugging of implementation code and auxiliary scripts used for data processing and visualization;
- producing initial drafts of textual passages from outlines, notes, bullet points, and partial material supplied by the author, who then reviewed, fact-checked, restructured, and edited each passage before inclusion;
- revising the linguistic form—grammar, phrasing, register, and clarity—of existing text;

The intellectual content of this thesis is the author's own. Generative AI tools were not used to formulate the research questions, to conceive the methodological contributions of this work nor to produce the mathematical derivations, to design the experimental protocols, or to interpret the empirical results presented in this document.

All AI-generated suggestions were critically reviewed and, where retained, edited by the author. The author assumes full responsibility for the content, the accuracy, and the intellectual integrity of this thesis.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

A wide range of systems — social groups, financial markets, transportation infrastructures, the brain, online platforms — can be usefully described as *networks* (or *graphs*): a set of *nodes*, each representing an entity (a person, an account, a neuron, a station, etc.), connected by *edges* that represent the interactions or relationships between them (friendships, transactions, synaptic links, train lines, etc.). This abstraction has fueled an active and now mature field of research, *network science*, dedicated to extracting structural and functional information from relational data [1–3]. Among the patterns that recur across domains, *community structure* — groups of nodes whose interconnections set them apart from the rest of the network — is one of the most prominent. Identifying such groups reveals functional modules in biology, peer groups in social systems, topical clusters in information networks, and so on; it has become a standard exploratory tool whenever relational data is available [4, 5].

For *static* networks, among the most popular tools are Newman’s *Modularity* [6], which provides a principled quality function for *partitions* (groupings of the nodes into communities), and the *Louvain* [7] algorithm, which optimizes it greedily and at scale, thereby uncovering meaningful communities. Beyond their methodological merits, the success of these tools owes much to their practical accessibility: they are available off-the-shelf in standard libraries and are routinely applied by domain practitioners with modest network-analysis expertise.

The static graph abstraction is, however, only a first approximation. Most real-world systems are inherently *dynamic*: friendships form and dissolve, communications burst and fade, transactions occur at specific moments, transportation flows shift with the time of day. Modern data collection increasingly captures these dynamics at fine temporal resolution [8], and an active body of research has set out to handle them explicitly, under the banner of *temporal networks* [9, 10]. Aggregating this temporal

information into a static graph — or even into a sequence of *snapshots*, each obtained by treating all interactions occurring within a chosen time window as if they formed a single static network — is known to distort the structural picture in non-trivial ways [11–13].

This observation argues for a more demanding methodological standard: rather than choosing a time scale at which to aggregate the data, an analytical method should operate at the *native time precision* at which the data was collected. Temporal datasets are typically timestamped at fine granularity — to the second, the millisecond, or finer — and any prior aggregation discards information that was deliberately recorded. Operating at native time precision means that no modeling decision concerning the time scale is taken before the analysis itself begins: communities, paths, motifs, or any other derived structures are expressed directly in terms of the timestamped events, rather than in terms of an externally imposed time grid. The *link stream* framework [14] formalizes precisely this standpoint, by representing temporal data as a set of timestamped interactions and redefining classical network-analytical concepts at this same resolution. It is the perspective we adopt throughout this thesis.

Adopting link streams as our data representation, however, leaves open the question of analysis. More broadly: *what would a Modularity-and-Louvain-style approach look like for temporal networks?*

This is one specific instance of a broader question — that of *dynamic community detection* — which has motivated a substantial and active body of work [15, 16]. Among the various proposals, multilayer Modularity [17] is a particularly influential one, and arguably the closest in spirit to our goal: it directly extends the static Modularity framework to coupled snapshot sequences. Multilayer Modularity nonetheless inherits the time-scale problem of snapshot models, as do most other approaches in the field — whether based on tracking communities across independently computed snapshots, or enforcing smooth evolution across consecutive snapshots. Methods operating directly on link streams remain comparatively rare, and the existing ones typically address restricted subcases: static communities along a continuous timeline [18], flow-based communities defined at a chosen time scale of analysis [19], or communities defined only between interactions of non-zero duration [20]. Across all these proposals, none achieves, at the native time precision of the data, the combination of principled quality function, and broad applicability that has made static Modularity-Louvain a workhorse of applied network analysis. Designing such a method, in the most general relevant setting, is the central goal of this thesis.

1.2 The Diversity of Real-World Temporal Interactions

Designing a general-purpose method also requires acknowledging something about the data such a method should handle. Beyond the question of temporal granularity, real-world temporal interactions exhibit a striking qualitative diversity that is too often glossed over in the literature. Three modalities of interaction, in particular, need to be distinguished:

- **Instantaneous interactions** occur at a single point in time, with no measurable duration. An e-mail being sent, a financial transaction being executed, or a vote being cast are naturally described as instantaneous events.
- **Continuous interactions** extend over a time interval. Two colleagues sharing an office, two animals in physical proximity, or two accounts simultaneously following one another are interactions whose meaningful representation requires both a start and an end time.
- **Delayed (or latent) interactions** are interactions in which source and destination are temporally separated. A passenger boards a bus at one stop and alights at another after a measurable travel time; a parcel is shipped from one warehouse and received elsewhere later. The connection between the two endpoints is real, but its endpoints are bound to different nodes and separated by a non-trivial duration.

These modalities coexist with other commonplace features: interactions are often *weighted* (carrying a magnitude or duration), *directed* (with an explicit sender and receiver), and *multipartite* (connecting heterogeneous types of nodes such as users and posts, or consumers and products). A method that aspires to be a general tool for dynamic community detection should natively support this entire spectrum of features, rather than handle one or two of them and require destructive preprocessing for the rest.

1.3 Research Objectives

The overarching ambition of this thesis is to design a principled and broadly applicable method for dynamic community detection — one that operates at the native time precision of the data and that supports the full diversity of interactions just described. We organize this ambition around three research questions.

RQ1 — Quality function. *How can the notion of community quality be formalized for temporal networks at native time precision, in a way that extends classical Modularity to the dynamic setting?*

RQ2 — Optimization algorithm. *Can such a quality function be optimized efficiently with a greedy, Louvain-like procedure that operates directly on temporal data, without time discretization?*

RQ3 — Generality. *Can the resulting framework be extended to handle the full diversity of real-world interactions — weighted, directed, multipartite, and combining instantaneous, continuous, and delayed contacts — within a single coherent formalism?*

1.4 Contributions

The thesis presents three main contributions, each corresponding to one research question. The first two have been published; the third is under review at the time of writing.

C1 — Longitudinal Modularity.

We introduce *Longitudinal Modularity* (L-Modularity), a generalization of Newman’s Modularity to temporal networks expressed as link streams. L-Modularity is first defined for the canonical case of simple, instantaneous interactions, before being extended to richer settings in Chapter 5. It evaluates the quality of a dynamic partition without prior aggregation of the data: communities can be either short-lived or long-lived, and nodes can join or leave them at any time. We show that L-Modularity recovers classical Modularity in the static limit, and that it can be seen as a generalization of multilayer Modularity. We further show that L-Modularity satisfies a set of structural properties one should expect from a temporal community quality function. This contribution addresses RQ1.

C2 — LAGO: greedy optimization of L-Modularity.

We then introduce *LAGO* (Longitudinal Agglomerative Greedy Optimization), an algorithm for optimizing L-Modularity directly on link streams. LAGO is, to the best of our knowledge, the first algorithm to perform dynamic community detection at the native time precision by operating without any prior time discretization, and uncovering the exact moments at which nodes enter or leave communities. LAGO generalizes the agglomerative logic of Louvain to the continuous-time setting, and its modular design allows it to be combined with various greedy exploration strategies. The algorithm

is evaluated on synthetic benchmarks and real-world data, and is shown to recover temporally and topologically coherent communities. This contribution addresses RQ2.

C3 — A generalized framework for complex link streams.

The third contribution generalizes the framework beyond the case of simple, instantaneous, and homogeneous interactions. Building on existing extensions of the link stream framework to weighted, bipartite, and directed cases, we introduce a *generalized link stream* model that natively supports weighted, directed, and multipartite interactions, together with the three temporal modalities — instantaneous, continuous, and delayed — discussed in Section 1.2. We extend L-Modularity and LAGO to this generalized setting in such a way that the original formulations are recovered as special cases. The framework is validated on three real-world datasets that exemplify the targeted features: a directed and weighted voting network (Eurovision), a transportation network with delayed and continuous interactions (Citi Bike), and a bipartite social network (Bluesky). This contribution addresses RQ3.

Taken together, these three contributions provide a unified pipeline — from quality function to optimization algorithm to general modeling framework — that, to the best of our knowledge, is the first dynamic community detection approach to combine native time precision with broad support for the diversity of real-world temporal interactions. An open-source Python library to apply LAGO and compute L-Modularity is available at https://github.com/fondationsahar/dynamic_community_detection.

1.5 Outline of the Manuscript

The remainder of this manuscript is organized as follows.

Chapter 2 — Background. We review the conceptual and technical background needed to position our contributions: networks and their analysis, static community detection (with a particular focus on Modularity and Louvain), temporal network models, and existing approaches to dynamic community detection.

Chapter 3 — Longitudinal Modularity. We present L-Modularity in detail, including its formal definition, its connection with classical and multilayer Modularity, and the structural properties it satisfies. Experimental results illustrate the relevance of the quality function on synthetic and real-world link streams. This chapter is based on [21].

Chapter 4 — *LAGO*. We introduce the LAGO algorithm for greedy optimization of L-Modularity on continuous-time temporal networks. We discuss several greedy exploration strategies, evaluate the algorithm on synthetic benchmarks and real-world datasets, and analyze its behavior in comparison with snapshot-based approaches. This chapter is based on [22].

Chapter 5 — *A Generalized Framework*. We extend L-Modularity and LAGO to weighted, directed, and multipartite networks, and to instantaneous, continuous, and delayed interactions, within a single generalized link stream formalism. The framework is validated on three real-world datasets covering the full range of supported features. This chapter is based on [23].

Chapter 6 — *Conclusion and Perspectives*. We summarize the contributions of the thesis, discuss their limitations, and outline several directions for future work.

1.6 Industrial Context

This thesis was carried out in partnership with SAHAR, a company developing an analytics platform for the investigation of relational and temporal data drawn from multimodal sources.

SAHAR’s data consists of timestamped interactions between entities — messages, transactions, references, co-occurrences — and identifying coherent groups of these entities over time is a recurring analytical need. The methodological gaps that motivate this thesis are encountered routinely on such data. For confidentiality reasons, the specifics of SAHAR’s applications and data are not discussed in this manuscript.

A portion of the doctoral work was carried out within the company, alongside the academic research. This applied experience provided regular contact with real-world data and use cases: it informed the choice of questions addressed but did not shape the scope of the contributions, which are presented in domain-general form.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Community Detection in Static Networks

Community detection is the problem of partitioning the nodes of a graph into groups whose interconnections set them apart from the rest of the network. This definition admits many different formalizations, which is why the literature is large and taxonomically diverse. The section first discusses the “goodness” of a community structure (Section 2.1.1), then surveys the main families of methods (Section 2.1.2), and finally develops the specific family on which the thesis builds (modularity and greedy optimizers, Section 2.1.3). Hierarchical methods are out of scope and the temporal extension is the subject of the section 2.3.

2.1.1 On the notion of community structure

There is no single agreed definition of what counts as a community. The literature offers several: a community can be a set of nodes more densely connected internally than externally; a set of nodes whose connectivity pattern is statistically distinct from the rest of the network; or a region where a walker on the network tends to “stay”. Each detection method adopts one such answer, with its own implicit modeling choices. These choices become explicit in the taxonomy presented in Section 2.1.2, where each methodological family is characterized by its underlying assumptions. Here we also adopt the point of view that external ground truths should not be used to arbitrate between competing operational definitions [24], because they do not rely on topological criteria alone. The taxonomy that follows is therefore different answers to the question “what does good even mean?”, rather than different algorithms for the same underlying task.

Given the plurality of operational definitions, how should one assess whether a partition is good? No single metric is decisive: quality functions, clustering-similarity scores against ground-truth labels, and topological properties of the resulting commu-

nity structure each capture only a partial view, and a descriptive approach combining multiple measures is often necessary [25]. Among these, *quality function* are the most widely used in practice. They serve two roles: they score any partition under a given definition of “good”, and they define the optimization objective of many detection methods. This dual role is a limitation for evaluation — methods are typically evaluated by the same function they were designed to optimize — but a principled basis for detection: the choice of quality function is the choice of what “good” means, made explicit.

2.1.2 A taxonomy of community detection methods

This section presents some of the most popular community-detection methods. We first focus on methods with no global objective function (Section 2.1.2.1), which define a community through local rules — a k -clique union, a dense seed expansion, a consensus of local labels. We then present methods with a global objective function (Section 2.1.2.2), which define a community as whatever optimizes a scalar score: a cut, a likelihood, a modularity, a description length. More comprehensive coverage is available in dedicated surveys [4, 5].

This section is far from exhaustive; for instance, we do not discuss methods that introduce a modeling layer between the graph and the partition: graph neural-network and embedding-based methods [26], which cluster nodes in a learned latent space; we do not discuss other interesting methods such as matrix factorization [27], which approximates the adjacency matrix as a product of low-rank factors; and game-theoretic approaches [28], which model communities as stable coalitions of a cooperative game. The thesis focuses on methods without such an intermediate representation: communities are defined directly from the graph’s structure.

2.1.2.1 Methods without a global objective function

Methods in this class define a community through local rules or structural criteria. The output is whatever the procedure produces; there is no scalar score that ranks partitions on the whole graph. Two representative approaches are covered: density-based methods, which identify dense subgraphs by structural criteria, and label propagation, which converges to a local consensus by local update rules.

Density-based and local methods. Density-based methods define a community as a structurally dense subgraph — a region where cliques (fully connected subgraphs) or near-cliques overlap, or a subgraph exceeding a density threshold — without requiring a global partition of the nodes. The emblematic example is the Clique Percolation Method (CPM) [29], which identifies communities by rolling a k -clique through the

graph; local variants grow a community from a single seed node without constructing a partition of the whole graph [30]. The distinctive strength of this family is native support for overlapping communities, which partition-based methods do not provide. Its weaknesses are several: clique enumeration is worst-case exponential in clique size, and CPM in particular is strongly sensitive to the user-chosen k parameter and leaves large fractions of nodes unassigned on large empirical networks with reasonable values of k [31]. In short, density-based methods are committed to a structural definition: a community is a region of high local connectivity — a clique union, a dense seed expansion — valuable wherever such regions overlap.

Label propagation. Label propagation defines communities through iterative local label updates. Each node is initialized with a unique label; at each iteration, every node adopts the label most common among its neighbors, with ties broken randomly. The process is repeated until convergence, and the final label classes are the communities [32]. This popular and efficient method is, however, known to be sensitive to update order and to exhibit degenerate behavior on large empirical graphs [33]. In short, label propagation is committed to a local-consensus definition: a community is a set of nodes that converge on the same label under local update rules.

2.1.2.2 Methods with a global objective function

Methods in this class define a community as whatever optimizes a global score on the network. The score encodes the family’s modeling assumption. Detection becomes optimization, and the resulting partition can be compared across methods through the score’s value. Three representative approaches are covered: spectral approach to graph partitioning, statistical inference via stochastic block models, and greedy optimization of a quality function.

The thesis builds on this class of methods because the global objective makes the modeling assumption explicit and gives a common scale on which to compare partitions. Since the thesis aims for broad applicability, each of the three approaches is discussed along three criteria reflecting common features of real networks: its capacity to handle *weighted* edges (W), *directed* edges (D), and *multipartite* node sets (M).

Spectral approach to graph partitioning. Spectral methods start from a *graph-cut objective* on the discrete partition — canonically the *normalized cut*, which sums each group’s inter-group edge weight normalized by its total degree [34]. Direct minimization is NP-hard [35], but a continuous relaxation has a closed-form solution: the eigenvectors associated with the smallest non-zero eigenvalues of a Laplacian-like operator derived from the graph. The algorithm has two steps. First, these eigenvectors

define a low-dimensional embedding of the nodes. Second, a discrete partition is recovered by clustering this embedding, typically with k -means — a heuristic step that does not globally minimize the original cut. The family handles weighted (W) graphs directly: the Laplacian is defined for any non-negative weight matrix. Directed (D) and multipartite (M) settings have been addressed by dedicated extensions [36, 37]. In short, the spectral approach is committed to a graph-partitioning definition: a community is a group of nodes weakly connected to the rest of the network, recovered as a cluster in the spectral embedding induced by a graph operator. However, the family requires the number of communities k as input; the eigengap heuristic gives a principled choice for well-separated structure but is unreliable on graphs with ambiguous boundaries [35].

Statistical inference: stochastic block models. Stochastic block models (SBMs) assume the graph is generated by a probabilistic process: each node has a latent community label, and edges depend on these labels [38]. Community detection becomes *inference*: the objective is to recover the labels that best explain the observed graph. The probabilistic formulation supports likelihood-based tools, including tests for whether a community structure is present at all [39]. SBMs handle directed (D) networks through asymmetric block-edge rates [40]; weighted (W) networks are covered by weighted SBM variants [41]; and multipartite (M) networks require explicitly typed or layered variants [42]. Inference also requires specifying the number of blocks; nonparametric Bayesian formulations address this via model-selection priors [43]. In short, the SBM family is committed to a generative definition: a community is a set of nodes with the same statistical relationship to the rest of the graph.

Greedy optimization of a quality function. Methods in this family combine two elements: a *quality function* that scores partitions, and an optimizer that searches the partition space for high-scoring solutions. The two are in principle decoupled: a given optimizer can be applied to different quality functions, and vice versa. The instances below share the same optimization template: greedy local moves on a discrete partition.

The most popular of all objective functions is certainly *Modularity*, defined quickly as the difference between the observed number of edges inside communities and the expected number of edges under a null model [6]. We will describe Modularity in more details in section 2.1.3. We can mention here a few other popular objective functions: the *Constant Potts Model* is a resolution-parameterized objective thought to mitigate the well known resolution limit of modularity [44]. The *map equation* (Infomap) is a method grounded in information theory, whose principle is to find the partition allowing the best compression of the description of a random walker on the graph [45]. Since

randomness cannot be compressed, this method does not discover communities in random networks, unlike modularity. *Markov stability* is a quality function parameterized by the time scale of a Markov diffusion process on the graph [46]; it recovers modularity at $t = 1$ [47]. *Surprise* measures the statistical significance of within-community edges under a null model [48]. All these objective functions are at least as valid as modularity, and some of them propose elegant solutions to well-known limits of modularity. However, modularity remains one of the most popular objective functions. Due to its simplicity, it is especially attractive in the context of proposing an extension to a new context, in particular a context as complex as temporal networks. Adapting other objective functions would of course be a relevant extension of the current work.

The greedy optimizers for static networks—Louvain, Infomap optimizer, and Leiden—scale well to large networks [7, 45, 49]. A quality function can be adapted to a new graph type—weighted (W), directed (D), bipartite, multipartite (M)—through internal modifications to the objective function, while the optimizer stays almost the same.

2.1.3 Modularity and greedy optimization methods

This section presents the foundations on which the thesis’s contributions build: modularity, the objective function it maximizes, and three closely related greedy optimizers, which we name according to the methods they were introduced in: Louvain, Infomap, and Leiden. Modularity is the most widely used quality function for community detection [4, 5], with well-documented extensions to weighted (W), directed (D), and multipartite (M) graphs (Section 2.1.3.1). Wide adoption and broad extensibility make it a natural entry point for a method that aims to be broadly applicable.

2.1.3.1 Modularity

The modularity of a community structure \mathcal{C} over a network is based on the comparison of two terms: the observed number of edges within communities and their expected numbers based on a random null model. The higher the modularity, the more exceptional is the density inside communities, given the reference null model. Modularity was first introduced using the configuration model as reference [6], which rewires edges while preserving the degrees.

Definition. Consider a network with node set V and adjacency matrix A , where A_{uv} denotes the weight of the edge between u and v (or simply 1 if the network is unweighted). The degree of a node is $k_u = \sum_v A_{uv}$, and the total number of edges is

$m = \frac{1}{2} \sum_u k_u$. With this notation, modularity is defined as

$$Q(A, \mathcal{C}) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u, v \in C} \left[A_{uv} - \frac{k_u k_v}{2m} \right], \quad (2.1)$$

The quantity inside the brackets is the difference between the observed and expected edge weight between u and v under the null model. High values of Q indicate an exceptional amount of edges within communities compared to what the null model predicts.

Limits. Modularity has well-documented limitations. Fortunato & Barthélemy [50] showed that modularity maximization may fail to resolve small communities in large networks: small but well-defined communities are systematically merged with neighboring communities, and the effect is intrinsic to the null model, not an artifact of the optimizer. Reichardt & Bornholdt [51] introduced a resolution parameter γ that rescales the null contribution (formalized in the next paragraph), and Arenas, Fernández & Gómez [52] proposed analyzing the partition landscape across resolutions. Neither approach actually solves the resolution limit: Lancichinetti & Fortunato [53] showed that no single resolution value recovers networks with heterogeneous community sizes — low values merge small communities, while high values split large ones. Good, de Montjoye & Clauset [54] showed that many partitions can score near the maximum modularity; heuristic algorithms can therefore return different partitions depending on starting point and tie-breaking rules. Modularity is also restricted in scope: by construction, it scores only assortative communities (where within-group connectivity exceeds expectation), missing disassortative or core-periphery patterns that SBM approaches, for instance, are capable of recovering.

Two further concerns surface in practice. First, modularity reaches positive values on random graphs with no planted community structure [55]: even random edge placement creates coincidental concentrations that the optimizer locks onto and reports as communities. This is a symptom of modularity being a descriptive criterion rather than an inferential one — the score does not by itself distinguish genuine structure from noise [56]. Second, modularity-optimal partitions can be brittle under small edge perturbations, especially when the underlying community structure is weak; Karer, Levina & Newman [57] propose using robustness under perturbation as a test for whether the detected structure is significant. That said, modularity-based methods remain useful when the goal is descriptive rather than inferential: they reliably produce assortative partitions that align with intuitive notions of community structure and support summarization and visualization tasks.

Extensions. The original definition has been extended in several directions: a resolution parameter γ addresses the resolution limit, and weighted (W), directed (D), and multipartite (M) graph types are accommodated by adjusting the null model. Below we show how these extensions can be combined into a unified formulation.

A resolution parameter γ controls the characteristic size of detected communities and partially alleviates the resolution limit. Reichardt & Bornholdt [51] introduce γ by rescaling the null contribution, generalizing modularity (2.1) to

$$Q(A, \mathcal{C}, \gamma) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u, v \in C} \left[A_{uv} - \gamma \frac{k_u k_v}{2m} \right]. \quad (2.2)$$

Setting $\gamma = 1$ recovers the original Newman–Girvan formulation; $\gamma > 1$ favors finer partitions, $\gamma < 1$ coarser ones. Of course, γ -parameterization comes at a cost: γ is a parameter that must be chosen, and no single value is objectively correct. It is thus a way to tune the size of communities, and not a solution to the resolution limit problem of modularity.

When A_{uv} encodes interaction strengths rather than binary indicators, the same formulation (2.2) naturally extends to *weighted networks* (W). In this setting, we denote the total weight of the network as $w = \frac{1}{2} \sum_u k_u$, which equals the total number of edges m when all weights are set to 1.

For *directed networks* (D), the adjacency matrix is asymmetric ($A_{uv} \neq A_{vu}$ in general) and each node has an out-degree $k_u^{\text{out}} = \sum_v A_{uv}$ and an in-degree $k_u^{\text{in}} = \sum_v A_{vu}$, with total weight $w = \sum_u k_u^{\text{out}} = \sum_u k_u^{\text{in}}$. Leicht and Newman [58] proposed a tailored null model based on separate in- and out-degree sequences:

$$Q(A, \mathcal{C}, \gamma) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u, v \in C} \left[A_{uv} - \gamma \frac{k_u^{\text{out}} k_v^{\text{in}}}{w} \right]. \quad (2.3)$$

The undirected formulation is recovered by treating each undirected edge as two reciprocal directed edges, so that $k_u^{\text{in}} = k_u^{\text{out}} = k_u$.

Some networks involve nodes of different kinds — such as users and items, or genes and diseases — and interactions only occur between different kinds. For such *multipartite networks* (M), the node set is partitioned into disjoint types $\{V_1, \dots, V_p\}$ and edges exist only between nodes of different types ($A_{uv} = 0$ whenever $u, v \in V_i$); the *bipartite* case corresponds to $p = 2$. Barber [59] introduced a modularity formulation that restricts the null model to respect this constraint: since no edges can exist within the same type, the expected number of intra-type edges is set to zero, and the null model only redistributes edges across types. This is achieved by setting $b_{uv} = 1$ when u and v belong to different types and 0 otherwise, effectively masking same-type pairs from the expectation term.

We propose the following *unified formulation*:

$$Q(A, \mathcal{C}, \gamma) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u, v \in C} \left[A_{uv} - \gamma b_{uv} \frac{k_u^{\text{out}} k_v^{\text{in}}}{w} \right]. \quad (2.4)$$

Setting $b_{uv} \equiv 1$, $k_u^{\text{in}} = k_u^{\text{out}} = k_u$ and therefore $w = 2m$ recovers (2.1).

Other extensions of modularity exist, notably for signed networks [60], overlapping communities [61], and higher-order structures [62]. Since incorporating these formulations would require nontrivial adaptations of the methodology considered in the thesis, we do not discuss them further. Their treatment would require a separate methodological development.

2.1.3.2 Optimizers

Modularity scores partitions; finding a high-scoring one requires an optimization algorithm. Since modularity maximization is NP-hard [63], widely used methods rely on greedy heuristics. The three covered here — Louvain [7], the Infomap optimizer [45], and Leiden [49] — share a common algorithmic template: a greedy local-move phase that reassigns nodes between communities, alternated with an aggregation phase that contracts each community into a single node of a reduced graph. In what follows, references to Louvain, Infomap, or Leiden denote the algorithmic procedure itself, independent of the quality function being optimized; the template is decoupled from the objective and can optimize modularity equally well.

Louvain. Blondel et al. [7] proposed an iterative, agglomerative procedure that maximizes modularity by alternating two phases until no further improvement is possible. In the first phase, each node is initially assigned to its own community; then, in random order, each node is considered for reassignment to the community of one of its neighbors, choosing the move that maximizes the gain in modularity. The pass is repeated until no reassignment improves modularity. In the second phase, a new graph is built whose nodes are the communities identified in the first phase and whose edge weights aggregate inter-community link weights from the original graph. The first phase is then reapplied to this aggregated graph. The two phases alternate until modularity can no longer be improved. The procedure leverages the property that a partition defined on the aggregated graph preserves the modularity value of the corresponding partition on the original graph. Combined with the locality of modularity gain — the gain from a node’s reassignment depends only on its neighbors — this enables fast computation and makes community detection practical on large networks. Louvain accommodates weighted (W) and directed (D) networks without structural modification, since the network type only affects the gain formula used in the reassignment phase [64]. For

bipartite networks, the bi-Louvain variant [65] performs type-aware aggregation to prevent merging nodes of different types, and the extension to general multipartite (M) structures follows the same principle.

Infomap optimizer. Rosvall & Bergstrom [45] introduced Infomap as an optimizer for the map equation. It begins with a Louvain-style procedure — optimizing the map equation rather than modularity — to produce an initial hierarchical partition. A refinement phase then applies two steps iteratively. Single-node movements reassign nodes from the original graph between the top-level communities. Submodule movements run a Louvain-style procedure within each community to identify submodules that may then move to other communities. The two steps repeat until the map equation cannot be further optimized. The same algorithm can be applied to other objectives, such as modularity.

Leiden. Traag, Waltman & van Eck [49] proposed Leiden to address two limitations of Louvain that persist regardless of the quality function optimized: Louvain can return communities that are internally disconnected, and a single iteration is not guaranteed to strictly improve modularity. Leiden introduces two key changes. First, a refinement step is added between the local-move and aggregation phases of each Louvain iteration, splitting each community into its internally connected components before aggregation; unlike Infomap’s post-processing refinement, this step is embedded directly inside the Louvain template. Second, the local-move exploration is modified to maintain a dynamic set of candidate nodes for reassignment: when a node is moved, its neighbors are added back to the set, which both improves speed and helps avoid poor local optima. Leiden is in practice a drop-in replacement for Louvain, with comparable runtime and higher modularity on standard benchmarks.

2.2 Temporal Networks

A temporal network is a network whose structure or interactions vary over time, with examples ranging from face-to-face contacts and communication exchanges to transportation flows, biological interactions, and evolving social ties. Many real systems are inherently temporal, and analyzing them through static abstractions discards the temporal dynamics that shape their structure.

Real temporal networks display several properties that different representations encode with varying fidelity. This thesis focuses on the following seven properties:

(W) Weighted edges interactions differ in intensity.

(D) Directed edges interactions may be asymmetric.

- (M) **Multipartite structure** nodes belong to one or several distinct types.
- (I) **Instantaneous events** interactions occur at a single time point.
- (C) **Continuous contacts** interactions persist over a time interval.
- (L) **Delayed interactions** source and target are separated in time.
- (T) **Exact time** timestamps are preserved at their native resolution, without aggregation.

This list of properties is, of course, not exhaustive, but corresponds to the main ones we will consider in this thesis.

In this section we review the main formal representations proposed for temporal networks, progressing from static aggregation and snapshot-based representations (Section 2.2.1) to enriched formalisms (Section 2.2.2) and stream graphs (Section 2.2.3), and conclude with a synthesis (Section 2.2.4). At each stage we evaluate which of the seven properties can be captured and whether community detection methods have been developed within the formalism.

2.2.1 From static aggregation to discrete-time representations

Static aggregation. The simplest approach to analyzing a temporal network with static methods is to aggregate all interactions over the full observation period into a single static graph, where edges are either binary or weighted (W) by the number or total duration of interactions. This enables the direct application of the standard graph analysis toolbox—including classical community detection methods—without any adaptation. However, this projection systematically discards temporal information: distinct interaction sequences can produce identical static aggregates [9]. Full aggregation collapses instantaneous events (I) and continuous contacts (C) into a single weight, erases any trace of delayed interactions (L), and removes the temporal ordering (T) of interactions. Direction (D) and multipartite structure (M) may be preserved from the underlying graph construction.

Snapshot-based representations. Discrete-time representations introduce time by indexing the data over discrete moments rather than collapsing everything into one static graph. The most widely adopted approach is to organize the data into ordered sequences of snapshots—static graphs G_0, G_1, \dots, G_T , typically over a fixed node set, each representing the state of the network during a window of duration Δt [9]. The same discrete-time data can also be represented as a third-order tensor (source \times destination \times time) [66]. This representation requires a fixed node set.

Snapshots can fit the data naturally: in yearly co-authorship or monthly trade networks, Δt is given by the data. In other cases, the raw data is a stream of timestamped events—email exchanges, phone calls, face-to-face contacts—and the data has no native snapshot structure of its own. The practitioner must impose a window Δt and aggregate all events within it into a single graph.

With forced aggregation, temporal ordering within each window is erased, and the choice of Δt becomes a modeling decision that strongly affects network structural properties [11–13, 67]. Choosing Δt too small yields sparse snapshots with too few interactions per window to be analytically useful. A direct consequence is that the distinction between (I) and (C) collapses inside snapshots: a brief instantaneous event and a continuous contact lasting through the window both produce an edge present in that window, and duration is no longer encoded. Some work proposes diagnostics for evaluating when aggregation remains faithful [68, 69], or for choosing between snapshots and link stream representations (Section 2.2.3) [70].

These distortions propagate directly to community detection outcomes: communities that exist at different times within the same window are merged into a single snapshot, communities that span window boundaries are split across consecutive snapshots, and the detected structure depends on the arbitrary parameter Δt . Some communities may not be detectable at all: short-lived ones disappear into surrounding aggregation, and communities spread thinly across windows are never dense enough in any single window to be recovered.

Delayed interactions (L) could in principle be represented through edges between snapshots at different times—from a source node in G_i to a target node in G_j with $i \neq j$ —but this extension is not pursued in the snapshot literature. Multipartite structure (M) is inherited per snapshot from the underlying graph, since each snapshot is itself a static graph. Exact time (T) is preserved when snapshots align with natural time units, but lost when a practitioner-imposed Δt windows the data.

Despite these limitations, snapshot sequences are the dominant choice in practice: static network methods are directly applicable to each snapshot independently, so existing algorithms and intuitions carry over with minimal modification. For the same reason, snapshots are the *de facto* baseline in temporal community detection, where dynamic structure is typically recovered through post-hoc analysis of partitions found in each snapshot (see Section 2.3).

2.2.2 Beyond snapshots: toward exact temporal modeling

To overcome the limitations of discrete-time approaches, several formalisms have introduced richer temporal structure. Each was motivated by a specific problem and offers distinct tradeoffs between expressiveness and practical applicability.

Static-reduction representations. A different line of work seeks to encode a temporal network as a single static graph that retains its temporal information, so that standard static algorithms become applicable. The most direct way is to start from a snapshot sequence: stack the snapshots into a single supra-adjacency matrix and add interlayer edges between consecutive instances of the same node, encoding temporal continuity through edge weights. The construction is widely used in the multilayer-network literature and underlies some of the most popular temporal community detection methods. However, the construction inherits the discretization of its snapshot input. Time is also encoded into block indices and interlayer edges, no longer a separate dimension.

A different family of constructions avoids the snapshot step entirely, working directly on event-level data. Wehmuth et al. [71, 72] introduced *MultiAspect Graphs* (MAGs), where edges connect (node, time) pairs: $e = (u, t_a, v, t_b)$ links node u at time t_a to node v at time t_b . MAGs aim to unify the many temporal network representations under one algebraic object, where time is one dimension among several. Any MAG is isomorphic to a directed graph, which enables the reuse of static graph algorithms—at the cost of treating time as one component of node identity rather than a structural dimension. A related event-driven construction is given by Kostakos [73], where each event-bearing (node, time) pair becomes a node of the resulting graph; consecutive instances of the same original node are connected by waiting edges weighted by the time gap, and instantaneous interactions become unweighted edges. Mellor [74] pushes this idea further with *event graphs*, in which individual temporal events themselves become nodes of a static directed acyclic graph and edges connect temporally adjacent events.

The static-reduction approaches can, in principle, accommodate delayed interactions (L). For instance, in multilayer network graphs, one could encode (L) by introducing edges between (u, t_a) and (v, t_b) with $t_a \neq t_b$. Despite being a natural extension, this has not been pursued in the literature. MAGs, by contrast, support such delayed interactions natively through their tuple structure.

All these constructions build time into the static graph itself, into the nodes or into edge directions, rather than keeping it as a separate dimension. This makes them lossless or near-lossless and exposes the data to the full static toolbox. The decisive limitation is structural: the graph these constructions produce is not a direct model of the original network. Its nodes encode events or (entity, time) pairs, and its edges may include connections that encode time rather than real interactions. A community detected on such a graph cannot be read as a community of the temporal network without further interpretation.

Time-varying graphs. Casteigts et al. [75] introduced the *Time-Varying Graph* (TVG) formalism $\mathcal{G} = (V, E, \mathcal{T}, \rho, \zeta)$, where $\rho: E \times \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is a presence function indicating when each edge is active in continuous time, and $\zeta: E \times \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a latency function specifying traversal delay. The framework includes a classification of TVGs by how their connectivity varies over time—from networks that are always connected to those that are merely eventually connected. TVGs handle instantaneous (I) and continuous (C) contacts through continuous ρ , directed interactions (D) through ordered edge pairs, delayed interactions (L) through ζ , and exact time (T). Because ρ is binary, however, weights (W) and multipartite structure (M) are not natively encoded; both could be added as light extensions of the formalism (e.g. replacing ρ with a real-valued function, or partitioning V), but to the best of our knowledge this has not been pursued in published work. No community detection method has been developed within the TVG framework, which is oriented toward connectivity and routing problems rather than structural analysis.

2.2.3 Stream graphs and link streams

Latapy, Viard and Magnien [14] introduced *stream graphs*, defined as $S = (T, V, W, E)$ where T is a time interval, V a set of nodes, $W \subseteq T \times V$ specifies when each node is present, and $E \subseteq T \times V \otimes V$ specifies when each link is active—all over continuous time. A *link stream* $L = (T, V, E)$ is the special case where all nodes are present throughout T . Stream graphs generalize graph theory to continuous time, instead of reusing static tools on discretized data. Every graph-theoretic concept—density, clustering coefficient, connected components, cliques, paths—is redefined in continuous time, and the relationships between them carry over. Stream graphs were later extended to weighted, directed, and bipartite settings [76], and shown to include static graphs and time series as special cases [77]. This makes them the most general formalism in this review.

Among the formalisms reviewed, stream graphs offer the most suitable starting point to design a dynamic community detection applicable on most real datasets. They are continuous in time, keep nodes and edges as the natural units of analysis, and recover the standard formulations of static concepts (density, degree, weight) as continuous-time analogues. They preserve the temporal information without distortion: timestamps are not bucketed, ordering is not flattened, and durations are not collapsed into weights. Furthermore, a method working on a linkstream would also work on data originally collected as snapshot sequences. Stream graphs handle instantaneous events (I), continuous contacts (C), weighted edges (W), directed edges (D), bipartite structure (M), and exact time (T). The cost of this expressiveness is that existing static methods cannot be directly applied: every algorithm must be rethought

from scratch within the stream graph framework. Snapshots, by contrast, let the static toolbox carry over directly. Two properties remain open in the literature. Delayed interactions (L) are not modeled in the current formalism; as shown in Chapter 5, the framework can be naturally extended to encode (L) with minor extensions. General multipartite structure beyond the bipartite case is similarly not formalized in the literature, but is a straightforward extension also presented in Chapter 5.

2.2.4 Synthesis

Table 2.1: Temporal network formalisms confronted with the thesis’s modeling properties. \checkmark = explicit support, \sim = partial or implicit support, \times = not addressed. **W** = Weighted, **D** = Directed, **M** = Multipartite, **I** = Instantaneous, **C** = Continuous, **L** = Delayed/Latent, **T** = Exact time.

Formalism	W	D	M	I	C	L	T
Static aggregation	\sim	\sim	\sim	\times	\times	\times	\times
Snapshots	\sim	\sim	\sim	\checkmark	\times	\times	\times
Static reductions	\sim	\checkmark	\sim	\checkmark	\sim	\checkmark	\checkmark
TVG	\sim	\checkmark	\sim	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark
Stream graphs	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\sim	\checkmark

The formalisms reviewed (see Table 2.1) split along the line between formalisms that remain compatible with the static toolbox — at the cost of either aggregation (static aggregates, snapshots) or of treating time as a node attribute (static reductions) — and those that preserve continuous time as a structural dimension (TVGs, stream graphs), at the cost of requiring every method to be rebuilt from scratch.

While TVGs and stream graphs come closest to covering all seven properties, no single formalism in the review covers them all natively. Beyond per-property coverage, the central concern for representations of temporal data is structural: time should not be approximated through discretization, aggregation, or node relabeling. Among the structurally-faithful formalisms, TVGs and stream graphs are comparable starting points for the thesis’s contributions: both are amenable to extension toward the open properties. Stream graphs are nevertheless the working choice, because they redefine static graph-theoretic concepts in continuous time—a property the thesis builds on directly, extending static community detection methods to this setting.

2.3 Dynamic Community Detection

Dynamic community detection extends community detection to the temporal setting, where nodes and edges are situated in time and the partition itself can evolve over time. Static community detection lacks a fully settled formulation; the dynamic case

adds further open questions, such as when two communities at different times count as “the same”. The first part of this section (2.3.1) takes up these questions through a discussion of what makes a dynamic community “good”. The following parts then survey methods by computational scope: local methods (2.3.2) find solutions local in time or in topology, while global methods (2.3.3) operate jointly on the full temporal extent. A synthesis (2.3.4) closes the chapter.

Before turning to methods, this section discusses the properties that a general dynamic community detection framework should support.

Static networks already exhibit structural variety: edges may carry intensities (W) for **weighted** edges, **directions** (D) for sender–receiver relationships, or connect nodes of distinct types (M) for **multipartite** structure. These features carry over to the temporal setting and a general framework should support them.

We propose to split temporal interactions into three categories, that we believe to span the space of possible interactions: **instantaneous events** (I), i.e., point events in time, such as the sending of an email; **continuous-duration** contacts (C), i.e., interactions persisting over an interval, such as colleagues sharing an office; and **delayed or latent interactions** (L), i.e., interactions in which source and destination are temporally separated, such as a bus passenger’s trip between stops. Instantaneous events can be seen as a degenerate case of the other two — (I) is the degenerate case of (C) at zero duration and of (L) at zero lag. Classifying a method as working with either (I),(C), or (L) can be ambiguous. We choose to rely on the method’s model of the data. Snapshot-based methods illustrate this: within each slice, interactions are topologically equivalent to a static network and therefore considered (I).

As discussed in section 2.2, **exact time** (T) representation arises when interactions are represented without temporal aggregation, since aggregating events into time bins before processing loses the temporal structure the framework is meant to exploit.

Methods for detecting communities in temporal networks differ also on their capacity to model **evolving community membership** (E), i.e., to allow nodes to change communities over time. These eight axes of analysis are not exhaustive but cover the dimensions most directly relevant to this thesis; we will use them to characterize existing methods of the state of the art.

2.3.1 What makes a dynamic community “good”?

The very definition of what is a dynamic community, and how to represent it, has been discussed in various works [15, 78]. In this thesis, we restrict ourselves to the case of communities defined as *partitions of node-time*, or, said differently, evolving partitions of nodes. Indeed, in the static case, the most common approach to community detection is to search for a partition of the network, i.e., a solution in which each node belongs to

exactly one community. The natural extension of this definition to dynamic networks is a partition that evolves over time. Said differently, each node is assigned to a community for a period of time, and may belong to different communities at different times.

However, this natural extension to evolving partitions already raises an important question: should every node belong to a community at every period of the analysis? Indeed, it is common for real datasets to include nodes that are present and/or active at some periods, but absent or inactive at other periods. Let's consider for instance a social network: each user will join the platform at a time t_{start} , and might leave the platform or stop using it at period t_{end} . However, if we know only the interactions of the user, we do not know this period of activity. Imposing to assign a community to the node at every time step, including before t_{start} and after t_{end} might therefore be irrelevant, much as imposing to assign a community to a node without any neighbors in a static network. This example shows that extending the definition of partition to dynamic networks is not trivial, and might require making important modeling decisions.

Measurement of dynamic-community goodness raises its own challenges. In particular, the literature discusses a problem known as community smoothness [15]: at each instant the partition should reflect the topology of the graph; but over time the communities should also evolve smoothly and stay coherent. Both objectives can be optimized trivially, respectively i) by applying a static algorithm independently on each period of the graph, and ii) by searching for the best unique partition of the nodes for all times, without any change in affiliations —for instance by applying a static method on an aggregated graph. Dynamic community detection is instead searching for a sweet spot between the two, a good trade-off between communities that capture the structure of the network efficiently at a given instant while ensuring a smooth evolution of communities.

Three main types of failures of this double objective have been documented in the literature [16]: glitches (partitions oscillating without structural cause), oversimplification (smoothness masking real change), and identity loss (brittle matching across life-cycle events — birth, merge, split, resurgence).

After mentioning some of the most famous methods for community detection in dynamic networks, we will thus focus our analysis on methods having a global objective function to optimize, and thus a quantitative definition of what a good dynamic partition is.

2.3.2 Methods local in time or topology

Dynamic community detection methods can be local in time — processing one timestep or one event at a time rather than the full temporal extent at once — or local in graph structure — building communities from clique enumeration rather than from optimization over the whole partition.

2.3.2.1 Local-time methods

The oldest paradigm for dynamic communities with a local-time approach is known as *snapshot-and-match*: a static community detection algorithm is applied independently to each snapshot, and the resulting partitions are matched across consecutive snapshots — identifying which community at time t corresponds to which at $t+1$ — to reconstruct the temporal evolution of each community. Palla et al. [79] introduced this approach for clique-percolation communities, using a matching rule based on relative node overlap between communities at consecutive snapshots. Greene et al. [80] later generalized the approach to any static method, matching communities by Jaccard similarity across consecutive snapshots. The main advantage of this approach is that any static method can be reused unchanged, and the matching step is conceptually independent of the detection step. The main drawback is instability: small changes between successive snapshots can lead to large changes in the detected partition, which the matching step then interprets as community life-cycle events (births, merges, or splits) even when the underlying structure remained unchanged.

A second paradigm replaces the two-step detect-then-match pipeline with a single step in which detection at time t already incorporates the previous partition. On each snapshot, the algorithm optimizes a cost combining two terms: a partition-quality score on the current snapshot (e.g., modularity) and a penalty for differences with the previous partition [81]. This mitigates the instability of *snapshot-and-match*, but introduces a free parameter weighting the smoothness–fidelity trade-off. A multi-objective extension treats the two terms as competing objectives instead of summing them [82], trading the weight-parameter problem for the choice of which solution along the Pareto frontier to retain.

A third paradigm pursues coherence incrementally. At each timestep, the algorithm reuses the previous partition rather than starting from scratch; some variants re-optimize globally from this warm start, while others restrict updates to nodes affected by recent changes. Methods in this paradigm differ widely in how they define communities. *iLCD* [83] has no global objective function but rather local quality rules; it adds a node to an existing community when its connectivity to that community is strong enough. *TILES* [84] also processes interactions one at a time, propagating community labels from each new interaction’s endpoints outward through the network

— a single change can trigger further changes in adjacent nodes.

Some methods instead retain the idea of a global objective, typically the modularity. We can distinguish two approaches using modularity: the first re-optimizes on the whole network at each step but initializes the static algorithm with the previous partition: Aynaoud and Guillaume [85] initialize Louvain from the previous partition rather than from the standard singleton initialization, in which each node is in its own community. A risk of enforcing smoothness in this way is getting stuck in a local optimum and missing large structural changes. The second approach operates locally, reacting to specific edge events with dedicated update procedures: Görke et al. [86] propose adaptations of static modularity heuristics to streaming edge updates, with localized rules updating only regions near each edit. These methods have no mechanism to revisit previous assignments in distant parts of the network, even when accumulated edits make them suboptimal. Path-dependence is intrinsic to the incremental paradigm: the partition at time t depends on the order of all earlier updates, and earlier decisions cannot be revised. Subsequent work along both approaches has produced many refinements without resolving these paradigm-level limits.

All three paradigms support evolving membership (E) by construction. They share, however, several limitations. The snapshot-based variants inherit the costs of snapshot aggregation, which is incompatible with the exact-time (T) property that this thesis treats as mandatory. Their results also depend critically on the snapshot-aggregation strategy: the choice of window size and snapshot boundary placement shape the detected communities, and no principled way to make these choices exists across applications [11–13]. All three paradigms are also susceptible to cascade drift, with biases at early timesteps accumulating across the timeline as each step anchors on the previous one [16]. More fundamentally, a limit of all these smoothing approaches is that the smoothing is still performed *locally*, each community detection being performed at time t knowing graphs and partitions at $t - 1$, but without knowledge of network evolutions before or after. The remaining axes are less consistently handled: weighted (W) and directed (D) edges are typically supported, but multipartite structure (M) only by bipartite-specific variants. Continuous-duration interactions (C) are not natively handled: snapshot-based variants reduce them to (I) through aggregation, while event-stream variants assume (I) from the start. Delayed or latent interactions (L) are unaddressed.

2.3.2.2 Global-time but local-topology methods

The previous section discussed methods that were limited by a local analysis of time. Instead, in this section, we present methods that consider the whole duration of the temporal network at once, but that are limited by a local definition of communities, i.e., the absence of a global objective function. These methods are mostly based on

local patterns such as temporal cliques.

LSCPM [20] applies clique-percolation directly on the link-stream representation [14] (2.2.3), preserving exact time (T). It extends the clique-percolation approach and its snapshot-based dynamic versions [87] to link streams using Viard et al.’s generalization of cliques to the link-stream setting [88]: a temporal clique requires continuous interactions between all node pairs throughout the clique’s duration. Communities are unions of these k -cliques sharing $k-1$ nodes over overlapping intervals. LSFALO [89] removes LSCPM’s dependence on the clique-size parameter k , operating on link streams to identify maximal groups of nodes that interact together over the same time period. Both methods still rely on a user-chosen time window Δ that also determines the duration assigned to instantaneous events.

Both methods share a community definition that is locally dense in time and structure: sets of nodes whose pairwise interactions are dense over a continuous time interval, identified through clique enumeration. This definition is intrinsic to the method — communities are whatever the local rule produces — and not a global quantitative definition of what a good partition is. Clique percolation-based approaches are also known for their tendency to find communities that are either too small and dense —if based on large cliques— or too stretched out, with communities with little coherence when using small cliques as atomic elements. Other axes are not natively supported: cliques in their classical form are unweighted and undirected, and weighted (W), directed (D), and multipartite (M) structures require redefinitions (see Section 2.1.2.1) that neither method provides. Exact time (T) comes at the cost of (I): instantaneous events must be assigned an arbitrary duration to become continuous-duration contacts (C) before clique enumeration can apply. Evolving membership (E) is supported through time-interval communities.

2.3.3 Global methods

Global methods treat the temporal network as a whole, jointly across time and topology: the partition is determined by the optimization of a global function expressing its own definition of “good” dynamic communities. We divide existing methods in two categories: (i) Static-reduction methods build a static object from the temporal data and adapt a static method to it; (ii) native-temporal methods build time into the model itself, rather than handling it through a static reduction.

The section that follows reviews the most closely related methods, identifies their strengths and limits, and notes where they have inspired the contribution proposed in this thesis.

2.3.3.1 Static reduction

Static-reduction methods transform the temporal graph seen as a series of snapshots $G_t = (V_t, E_t), G_{t+1} = (V_{t+1}, E_{t+1}), \dots$ into a single static graph, representing both time and topology. More precisely, the most common construction consists in building a single static graph $G' = (V', E')$ in which the set of nodes V' is composed of time-nodes (u, t) , with $u \in V_t$, and edges in E' are either coming directly from the snapshots themselves (i.e., representing topological relations) or encode temporal relations, typically by connecting the same nodes in adjacent snapshots of the resulting graph, e.g., (u_t, u_{t+1}) . This network is commonly encoded in a so-called *supra-adjacency matrix* encoding both original static topology and time in a single supra-network. The idea is that a static method can be later used in this supra-network to uncover communities of time-nodes, interpreted as dynamic communities.

Static community-detection objectives have been extended through this framework. The most known such methods is the multislice modularity [17], detailed below. The same mechanism has been used to adapt Infomap and the map equation [90, 91].

Mucha et al.'s [17] multislice modularity extends the modularity objective to any multilayer object, and temporal networks are represented as special case of multilayer graphs. The quality function reads

$$Q = \frac{1}{2\mu} \sum_{ijsr} \left[\left(A_{ijs} - \gamma_s \frac{k_{is}k_{js}}{2m_s} \right) \delta_{sr} + \delta_{ij} C_{jsr} \right] \delta(g_{is}, g_{jr}), \quad (2.5)$$

where A_{ijs} is the adjacency of slice s , the first bracket yields a slice-local Newman–Girvan modularity with resolution γ_s , C_{jsr} is the interslice coupling weight between slices s and r , conventionally restricted to successive snapshots in the temporal sequence ($|r - s| = 1$), and the Kronecker $\delta(g_{is}, g_{jr})$ is unity when nodes i, j in slices s, r share a community assignment, and zero otherwise. The $1/2\mu$ normalization sums over all intralayer and interlayer edge weights. The objective is native on weighted edges (W) and produces evolving memberships (E) by allowing each slice its own partition. Directed (D) and multipartite (M) structures are not incorporated into the proposed multislice formula but extend naturally as in static modularity. The interslice coupling parameter C_{jsr} operationalizes the smoothness-versus-fidelity trade-off raised in the goodness discussion: higher couplings favor temporal continuity, lower couplings allow per-slice fidelity. Methodological diagnostics for the interslice coupling parameter and the null-model choices have been provided [92, 93]. This method inspires the contribution proposed in Chapter 3, which redefines the temporal smoothness term for the link-stream setting.

The operation of reduction into a single graph has structural costs. If the data is not originally in the form of snapshots, aggregating data into snapshots loses continuous-

duration contacts (C) and exact time (T): once data is binned, neither contact durations nor relative order inside the aggregation window survive. The optimization treats intra-layer (interaction) and interlayer (temporal-continuity) edges as undifferentiated graph edges, flattening time into another structural dimension and losing its directional, asymmetric character. Delayed or latent interactions (L) are missing but not structurally impossible: extending the adjacency A_{ijs} to a cross-slice form A_{ijsr} with $r > s$ would encode an interaction from node i at slice s to node j at slice r . Yet to the best of our knowledge, no published method explored this possibility; the convention restricts interslice couplings to copies of the same node at adjacent times.

2.3.3.2 Native temporal methods

Native-temporal methods operate directly on the temporal data without reducing it to a static object first.

Stochastic block models for temporal networks. Stochastic block models (SBMs) fit communities to a network by inferring the parameters of a generative process that most likely produced the observed data. Three trends have emerged in adapting SBMs to temporal networks. Matias and Miele [94] model the snapshot sequence with a discrete-time dynamic SBM in which each node can switch community from one snapshot to the next, with switch probabilities depending only on the current community. Memberships are dynamic, but exact time (T) is lost to the snapshot framing. Matias et al. [18] take the opposite trade-off with a continuous-time SBM: interactions between two nodes occur at random over time, with a rate that depends on the communities of the two nodes and can vary over the timeline. Exact time (T) is reached natively, but at the cost of fixed memberships, so evolving membership (E) is absent. Peixoto and Rosvall [95] reach both (T) and (E) by modeling edges as an ordered event sequence: each new edge depends on a number of recent past interactions, with that number inferred from the data, and the model identifies time points where the community structure abruptly reorganizes. The model fits best when events are spread evenly over time, since the method only considers the order of the sequence of interactions, and not the actual temporal distance between them; bursty or sparse activity weakens the predictive role of the recent past. The model does not optimize smoothness of node-level memberships: communities are defined on edge endpoints rather than directly on nodes, the structure is assumed stationary between change-points, and (E) is captured through these change-points rather than as gradual evolution.

None of these methods addresses delayed or latent interactions (L) or multipartite structure (M). Generative methods rest on a global objective, but no formulation reviewed here captures gradual membership evolution (E) while preserving exact time (T).

Tensor factorization. Tensor factorization treats the temporal network as a 3-dimensional array of interaction values indexed by (node, node, time), and decomposes it into a sum of a few components that approximates the original [96]. Constraining the representation to a few components forces them to capture the patterns most explanatory of the interactions. Each component represents one community: it specifies the degree to which each node belongs to that community and the community’s activity profile over time. Weighted (W) and directed (D) edges are encoded natively in the tensor values, and the time profile gives a soft form of evolving membership (E) through community-level activity changes rather than node-level reassignment. The method assumes that all interactions are between entities of the same kind, leaving multipartite structure (M) unaddressed. The (node, node, time) encoding has no place for separate source time and destination time, so delayed or latent interactions (L) are also unaddressed.

Flow stability. Bovet, Delvenne, and Lambiotte [19] introduce flow stability for dynamic community detection. A random walker diffuses on the temporal network, respecting the order in which edges appear. Communities are groups of nodes among which the walker remains likely to stay over a chosen time scale, where the time scale is a tunable parameter that controls how long the walker is allowed to diffuse. The method yields two partitions — one for the forward direction of time, one for the backward direction — over the chosen interval. Flow stability is the temporal extension of the Markov-stability framework of Section 2.1.2.2; static stability at Markov time one reduces to a modularity-like form, but the temporal extension does not strictly reduce to modularity at any Markov time. Continuous-duration interactions (C) and exact time (T) are handled natively. Instantaneous events (I) are not native: they require extending each instant to a short interval, since a zero-duration event has no effect on the diffusion. Weighted (W) and directed (D) edges are not in the canonical formulation but extend naturally. Evolving membership (E) is captured at the two interval endpoints as forward and backward partitions, rather than as gradual evolution. Multipartite structure (M) and delayed or latent interactions (L) are unaddressed. Per run, the method returns only two partitions, so trajectories of evolving memberships must be reconstructed by repeating the method across successive intervals. The user must also specify the time scale, with no intrinsic guidance for the choice.

2.3.4 Synthesis

Table 2.2 summarizes the strengths and weaknesses of representative families and flagship contributions against the eight properties defined previously, using the three-valued grading also used in the table of the preceding chapter: ✓ for explicit support,

\sim for partial or implicit support, and \times for absent.

Table 2.2: **Coverage of dynamic community detection families and flagship contributions against the eight axes.** \checkmark = explicit support, \sim = partial or implicit support, \times = not addressed. The two core temporal properties are listed first, followed by the six extensions. **T** = Exact time, **E** = Evolving membership, **W** = Weighted, **D** = Directed, **M** = Multipartite, **I** = Instantaneous, **C** = Continuous, **L** = Delayed/Latent.

Family / Method	Core		Extensions					
	T	E	W	D	M	I	C	L
Local-time methods (2.3.2)	\times	\checkmark	\checkmark	\sim	\sim	\checkmark	\times	\times
LSCPM [20] / LSFALO [89]	\checkmark	\checkmark	\times	\times	\times	\sim	\checkmark	\times
Multislice modularity [17]	\times	\checkmark	\checkmark	\sim	\sim	\sim	\times	\sim
Snapshot SBM [94]	\times	\checkmark	\sim	\checkmark	\times	\sim	\times	\times
Continuous-time SBM [18]	\checkmark	\times	\sim	\checkmark	\times	\checkmark	\times	\times
Event-sequence SBM [95]	\checkmark	\sim	\sim	\checkmark	\times	\checkmark	\times	\times
Flow stability [19]	\checkmark	\sim	\sim	\sim	\times	\sim	\checkmark	\times

Exact time (T) and gradual evolving membership (E) are the foundational temporal properties of a dynamic community detection method. No surveyed method, however, defines a global partitioning objective directly on the temporal data that achieves both. SBM-based methods each trade off different limits: snapshot SBMs work on discretized snapshots, losing exact event timing; continuous-time SBMs assume memberships are fixed once and for all, so communities cannot evolve; event-sequence SBMs cluster edge endpoints rather than nodes directly, assume stationarity between change-points, and don't optimize smoothness of node-level memberships. Mucha et al.'s multislice modularity inherits the slicing artifact, collapsing per-snapshot times into slice indices. Flow stability produces only two partitions per run: one at the start of the link stream and one at the end. This gap motivates the contribution of this thesis: a modularity-based global partitioning objective for link streams that natively supports (T) and (E). The thesis defines L-Modularity (Chapter 3), optimized through a Louvain-style algorithm (Chapter 4).

Other properties are supported unevenly across methods. Weighted (W) and directed (D) edges are usually supported through small adjustments to underlying static machinery, not as native features. Multipartite structure (M) is rarely addressed, and delayed or latent interactions (L), to our knowledge, are not addressed in the surveyed literature. L-Modularity (Chapter 3) natively handles (I). Chapter 5 extends it along the other axes: (W), (D), and (M) reuse the established static-modularity variants, and (C) and (L) require only minor adjustments to the link-stream representation.

Chapter 3

Longitudinal Modularity, a Modularity for Link Streams

Most community detection methods for temporal networks operate on sequences of snapshots, which requires an arbitrary aggregation window and obscures fine-grained dynamics (Chapter 2). Link streams [14] avoid this by modeling the network as timestamped interactions (u, v, t) , but no quality function existed to evaluate dynamic community structures directly on a link stream.

This chapter — the first contribution of this thesis — introduces *Longitudinal Modularity* (L-Modularity), generalizing classical Modularity [6] to link streams without aggregation, and supporting community structures in which nodes may enter, leave, and re-enter communities at any time. Three desirable properties — independence to time-aggregation, smoothness incentive, and toposynchronous disconnection — are formally identified, and L-Modularity is shown to satisfy all three. Experiments on the SocioPatterns high school dataset illustrate its behaviour. This chapter is based on [21].

3.1 Definitions: Link Stream and Temporal Community

This section introduces the definitions and notation used throughout this chapter. We first formalize the link stream framework presented in Section 2.2.3, and subsequently discuss temporal communities.

Definition 3.1. A **link stream** L is defined by a triplet (T, V, E) where $T \subset \mathbb{R}$ is a time interval, V a finite set of $N \in \mathbb{N}$ nodes, and $E = \{(u, v, t) \in V^2 \times T\}$ a finite set of interactions.

In the chapter we focus on the case of simple dynamic graphs where interactions are instantaneous, undirected, and unweighted. Although this does not affect our contribution, T is considered to be discrete. Let us introduce some notations used in the following (see also Fig. 3.1) for link streams:

- Let $uv_t = 1$ if $(u, v, t) \in E$, else 0.
- For a subset of time $T' \subset T$, define $L_{uv, T'} = \sum_{t \in T'} uv_t$ as the number of interactions between nodes u and v over T' .
- Let $L_{uv} = L_{uv, T}$ denote the total number of interactions between nodes u and v .
- Similar to static graphs, let us introduce the degree of a node u :

$$k_u = \sum_{v \in V} L_{uv}, \quad (3.1)$$

and m the total number of interactions in the link stream:

$$m = \sum_{u \in V} k_u / 2 = |E|. \quad (3.2)$$

As discussed in Section 2.3.1, there are multiple ways to define temporal communities. In this thesis, we keep the principle of non-overlapping communities, yet allow additional two behaviors pertaining to time: i) communities may evolve with time, i.e., a community is a set of *node-time* pairs (u, t) , and ii) nodes may belong to no community over some periods. Indeed nodes might have long periods of inactivity (e.g., nights in a fine-scale dataset, or even nodes that have left the systems, without us having this information, e.g., a phone number that is no longer attributed), and it would make little sense to try to include those inactive nodes in another partition, much as it would not make sense to include a node without edges in a static partition. This leads us to propose the following definition.

Definition 3.2. A dynamic community structure \mathcal{C} over a link stream $L = (T, V, E)$ is a set of non-empty and mutually exclusive communities composed of sets of node-time pairs $\{(u_1, t_1), (u_1, t_2), \dots, (u_2, t_3), (u_2, t_4), \dots\}$.

Let us introduce the notations used in the following:

- $T_{u \in C} = \{t \in T \text{ s.t. } (u, t) \in C\}$ represents the times when a node u belongs to community C .
- $T_{uv \in C} = T_{u \in C} \cap T_{v \in C}$ denotes the times nodes u and v simultaneously belong to community C .
- $L_{uv \in C} = L_{uv, T_{uv \in C}}$ represents the number of interactions between nodes u and v within community C .
- $T_C = \bigcup_{u \in V} T_{u \in C}$ denotes the existence time of community C .
- $C_u = \{C \in \mathcal{C} \text{ s. t. } T_{u \in C} \neq \emptyset\}$ is the set of communities visited by node u .

Figure 3.1: **Link stream with temporal communities.** Illustration of a link stream with a community structure depicted in blue and red. The figure includes representations of temporal community notations. The total interactions between nodes b and c are quantified as $L_{bc} = 4$. Within community B , these interactions total $L_{bc \in B} = 3$. Additionally, the degree of node a is represented as $k_a = 8$.

3.2 Longitudinal Modularity

This section introduces the Longitudinal Modularity function, a generalization of Modularity [6] and Multislice Modularity [17] to the link stream framework. We first define an *abstract temporal modularity* formulation and subsequently derive its expression for link streams.

Modularity (see Section 2.1.3) of a community structure \mathcal{C} over a network is based on the comparison of two terms: the observed number $\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{C}}$ of edges within communities and their expected numbers $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{C}}$ based on a random null model. We can therefore express Modularity in a generic form as:

$$Q = \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{C}} - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{C}} \quad (3.3)$$

In the remainder of this section, we will show how we can formalize a generic form of temporal Modularity, as was done in Equation (3.3) for the static one. We will then propose an instantiation of this generic formula for link streams, L-Modularity.

3.2.1 Abstract Temporal Modularity

As discussed in Section 2.3.3, Multislice Modularity (hereafter, MS-modularity) [17] extends Modularity to temporal networks by jointly accounting for topological fidelity and temporal smoothness. It was originally expressed (Eq. 2.5) in a way which is specific to 1) a representation of dynamic graphs —sequences of snapshots—, 2) a specific null model —preserving degrees in each snapshots—, and 3) a particular way to ensure stable communities —inter-snapshot edges with tunable weights.

We observe that, as we have done with static Modularity in Eq. (3.3), the general principle of a dynamic Modularity can be expressed in an abstract way as: the observed number of edges within communities $\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{C}}$, minus their expected number $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{C}}$ based on a null model, plus a smoothness term $\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{C}}$, penalizing nodes changing communities:

$$Q = \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{C}} - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{C}} - \mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{C}} \quad (3.4)$$

In MS-Modularity (Eq. 2.5), $\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{C}}$ comes from the sum over edges present inside communities in each snapshot (A_{ijs}), the expected edges correspond to the expected number of edges in each snapshot given their degrees in that snapshot ($\frac{k_{is}k_{js}}{2m_s}$), and the smoothness term comes from inter-snapshot edges not being inside communities (ω_{irs}).

We observe however that this particular instantiation of the abstract temporal Modularity of Eq. (3.4) cannot work for link streams: since a valid graph does not exist at any given time t , it is not relevant to use the instantaneous degree, nor to represent a smoothness term as inter-temporal edges. Only $\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{C}}$, i.e., the observed number of edges

inside communities, remain a valid notion in link streams. As a consequence, we will in the following introduce instantiations of the expected number of edges \mathbb{E}_C and of the smoothness term \mathbb{S}_C tailored for link streams.

3.2.2 Internal Edges Count \mathbb{L}_C

Given our definitions of link streams and communities (Sec. 3.1), counting the number of edges inside communities is as simple as in static networks: an interaction uv_t belongs to a community C if both u and v belongs to C at time t . Since we defined $L_{uv \in C}$ the number of interactions between u and v in community C , the total number of internal interactions can be computed as:

$$\mathbb{L}_C = \sum_{u,v \in V^2} \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} L_{uv \in C} \quad (3.5)$$

3.2.3 Link Expectation Null Model

In static Modularity, the most referenced null model is the configuration model, which randomizes the edges while preserving the degree sequence of the nodes [6]. With the notations of Eq. (3.4), the expectation of the presence of an edge between nodes i and j in a community $C \in \mathcal{C}$, according to this null model is given by

$$\mathbb{E}[A_{ij}] = \frac{k_i k_j}{2m} \delta_{i \in C} \delta_{j \in C} \quad (3.6)$$

In other words, two nodes with high degrees are more likely to have a link between them. Conversely, observing a link between two nodes with low degrees is unexpected and may indicate the presence of a hidden community structure.

The expectation term of MS-Modularity in the sense of the abstract temporal modularity (Eq. (3.4)) is a function of the degrees of the nodes in each snapshot. With the notations of Eq. 2.5, the expected number of links between nodes i and j in a community C over a set of snapshots S is

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{s \in S} A_{ijs} \right] \propto \sum_{s \in S} \frac{k_{is} k_{js}}{2m_s} \delta_{is \in C} \delta_{js \in C} \quad (3.7)$$

In other words, the expected number of links is proportional to the sum of the expected numbers of links in each snapshot, with each snapshot's expectations determined by its specific configuration model. This approach is referred to as the SnapS null model in Gauvin et al. (2022) [97].

In the context of link streams, we consider the null model denoted as $p[k, E]$ in Gauvin et al. (2022) [97]. This null model preserves the total degree of each node, but not the temporal sequence of interactions. For convenience, we name this null model

the *longitudinal configuration model*, as it directly generalizes the configuration model used for static networks. Note that this null model can be used both for link streams or snapshots.

Compared with the null model used in MS-Modularity, it seems to better take into account the temporal nature of the data: if we imagine a temporal network in which a pair of nodes interact actively over short periods, while staying inactive during others, then using the Longitudinal Configuration Model as reference, we will naturally consider these periods of activity as exceptional. Instead, using MS-Modularity null model, the activity in each period is compared only with other nodes activity in that same period, and not with the activity of the same nodes in other periods.

The modularity expectation terms are typically derived directly from the null model, corresponding to the stationary probability of two random walkers arriving at each pair of nodes based on the transition probability given by the null model [46]. If we choose this approach, we must define transition probabilities between time instances for each node, thereby introducing artificial edges, which is precisely what we seek to avoid. We propose an alternative method, termed the *longitudinal expectation* approach. This approach constructs expectation terms based on the total duration of the link stream and multiplies them with temporal weights defined by node presence in communities. We present three versions of the expected number of interactions between nodes u and v in a community C .

3.2.3.1 The Co-Membership Expectation (\mathbb{E}_{CM})

(Eq. (3.8)) represents the straightforward intuition that two nodes can only interact in time ranges in which they are both present.

$$\mathbb{E}_{\text{CM}} [L_{uv \in C}] = \frac{k_u k_v |T_{uv \in C}|}{2m |T|} \quad (3.8)$$

For links streams, we remind that k_u and m follows Eq. (3.1) and Eq. (3.2).

3.2.3.2 The Joint Membership Expectation (\mathbb{E}_{JM})

(Eq. (3.9)), considers the overall structure of the community in a way that promotes stationary or nearly stationary communities, where nodes remain members for the entire duration of the community's existence. One could assume that, just as a "perfect" community in a static network is a clique disconnected from the rest of the graph, a "perfect" community in a link stream is a set of nodes with similar properties that remain unchanged—i.e., no node additions or removals—during its existence.

$$\mathbb{E}_{\text{JM}} [L_{uv \in C}] = \frac{k_u k_v |T_C|}{2m |T|} \text{ if } C \in C_u \cap C_v, \text{ else } 0 \quad (3.9)$$

3.2.3.3 The mean membership expectation (\mathbb{E}_{MM})

(Eq. (3.10)) expects the presence of edges to be proportional to the lifetimes of the two nodes within the community. It is calculated as the geometric mean of the two lifetimes.

$$\mathbb{E}_{\text{MM}} [L_{uv \in C}] = \frac{k_u k_v}{2m} \frac{\sqrt{|T_{u \in C}| |T_{v \in C}|}}{|T|} \quad (3.10)$$

Given that $|T_{uv \in C}| \leq \sqrt{|T_{u \in C}| |T_{v \in C}|} \leq |T_C|$, \mathbb{E}_{MM} can be interpreted as a compromise between \mathbb{E}_{CM} —that may promote overly erratic temporal communities— and \mathbb{E}_{JM} —that promotes temporal communities with little or no evolution.

We can note that, in the special case where two nodes belong to a community at the same times, \mathbb{E}_{MM} is equivalent to \mathbb{E}_{CM} . Conversely, if one impose communities to stay unchanged during their time of existence, then $\mathbb{E}_{\text{MM}} = \mathbb{E}_{\text{CM}} = \mathbb{E}_{\text{JM}}$. Furthermore, if there is only one time step in the link stream, they are all equivalent to the expectation of the Modularity (Eq. (3.6)), which is in line with our objective of generalization from static graphs to link streams.

3.2.4 Smoothness Term

With no smoothness term for community discontinuities, modularity does not promote communities that are continuous over time (see Section 3.3). We argue that the purpose of considering temporal community structures is to capture information on their lifecycle, which necessitates communities that are continuous over time.

MS-Modularity smoothness term is based on the creation of interslice couplings between successive temporal instances of each node, then sums the weights of these artificial edges that fall in-between communities, i.e., when a node changes affiliation between one snapshot and the next. As a consequence, the more nodes change community, the greater the term. Noting ω_{urs} the interslice weight of a node u between snapshots r and s , MS-Modularity smoothness term is expressed as

$$\mathbb{S}_C \propto \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u \in V} \sum_{r, s \in \mathcal{S}^2} \omega_{urs} \delta_{us \in C} \delta_{us \in C} \quad (3.11)$$

By definition, in temporal networks, $\omega_{urs} = 0$ if $|r - s| > 1$, i.e., when snapshots r and s are not successive.

In our approach, it is essential to address the continuity of communities without relying on artificial temporal edges between time steps. To achieve this, we propose calculating the **Community Switch Count** (CSC), denoted as η_u , for each node u . The CSC represents the number of times a node transitions out of a community and

subsequently joins another community. More precisely, η_u is the number of communities visited by node u , minus one. This count also accounts for instances where a node revisits the same community multiple times. Fig. 3.2 illustrates examples of the CSC. In the critical case where nodes change communities at each interaction, the following inequality holds: $0 \leq \eta_u \leq k_u - 1$ for each node u , and therefore $0 \leq \sum_{u \in V} \eta_u \leq 2m - N$.

To maintain generality, we propose measuring the time discontinuity of a dynamic community structure with

$$\rho(L, \mathcal{C}) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{u \in V} \eta_u(\mathcal{C}) \quad (3.12)$$

where m follows the definition of Eq. (3.2).

We propose using this measure as a smoothness term $\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{C}}$ for L-Modularity in Eq. (3.3). In the scenario where there is only one time step in the link stream, $\rho = 0$, effectively generalizing Modularity. For the edge case mentioned above, ρ approaches 1. If there are even more discontinuities, ρ is not bounded. The smoothness term can be weighted according to specific requirements. A higher weight value results in greater penalization of discontinuities. For instance, with a weight of $2m$ and only one node changing community, L-Modularity will be less than 0, thereby promoting stationary communities. Similarly, with a weight of 2, L-Modularity will be less than 0 if, on average, nodes change community every two interactions. The weighting of the smoothness term may be refined, and its impacts should be explored in future research. In the end we propose using the following smoothness term, with a weighting parameter ω :

$$\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{C}} = \frac{\omega}{2m} \sum_{u \in V} \eta_u(\mathcal{C}) \quad (3.13)$$

Figure 3.2: **Community Switch Count (CSC) examples.** A 5-node link stream with 2 communities in red and blue. Nodes a and b leave the red community to form a two-node community in blue and then rejoin it ($\eta_a = \eta_b = 2$). Node e temporarily leaves the red community ($\eta_e = 1$). Nodes c and d never change community ($\eta_c = \eta_d = 0$), giving $\rho = 0.08$.

3.2.5 Definition

Based on the preceding discussion, we now propose a formal definition for Longitudinal Modularity.

Definition 3.3. Given a link stream L (following Def. 3.1) and a dynamic community structure \mathcal{C} (as per Def. 3.2), we define the Longitudinal Modularity as:

$$Q_{\star}(L, \mathcal{C}, \omega) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{\mathcal{C} \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u,v \in V^2} [L_{uv \in \mathcal{C}} - \mathbb{E}_{\star}[L_{uv \in \mathcal{C}}]] - \frac{\omega}{2m} \sum_{u \in V} \eta_u(\mathcal{C}) \quad (3.14)$$

where \mathbb{E}_{\star} is respectively Eq. (3.8), (3.9) or (3.10) for, respectively \mathbb{E}_{CM} , \mathbb{E}_{JM} or \mathbb{E}_{MM} .

The different Longitudinal Modularity versions will be evaluated against various desirable and undesirable properties in Section 3.3. Additionally, they will be illustrated through experiments in Section 3.4.

3.2.6 Extension to Multigraphs and Weighted graphs

Static Modularity naturally extends to multigraphs, by considering that the node degrees k_u correspond to the total number of edges, eventually repeated. Similarly, it naturally generalises to weighted graphs by using the node strengths (i.e., sum of weights of adjacent nodes) as values for k_u , and normalizing accordingly.

The same generalization can be done for L-Modularity. This generalization is particularly relevant in contexts in which temporal networks have been obtained by aggregating observations over periods of time, e.g., counting social interactions between people over a day, a week, or a month. In this situation, one can represent the strengths of these observations using multigraphs or weights. Note that when generalizing to any type of weighted graphs, in particular with weights lower than 1, it might be necessary to renormalize the smoothness term.

We will show in section 3.3.1 that, unlike MS-Modularity, L-Modularity provide coherent results in aggregated graphs compared with their non-aggregated versions (*Independence to time-aggregation property*).

3.3 Properties of dynamic communities

In the previous section, we proposed an adaptation of Modularity to link streams. In this section, we propose several properties that seem desirable for a definition of dynamic community structures in temporal networks and position L-Modularity relative to these properties.

Although the exact definition of what are *good* communities in static networks remains an open discussion, most authors agree on a general idea of groups *more*

strongly connected internally than the rest of the network. Modularity is a mathematical transcription of this general principle —one among others [35, 38, 56, 98]. One way to ensure that such a quantitative definition is compatible with the original intuition is to check that it respects some desired properties. For instance, one could say that Modularity in static networks respects the following properties:

- The score does not favor *trivial* solutions, such as having all nodes in the same community or each node in its own community.
- If there are two separated connected components in the graph, Modularity necessarily attributes a lower score to the partition merging them than to another one identical in other aspects, but keeping them independent.
- Communities are always denser than the overall network, as long as a solution is found with Modularity $Q > 0$.

We define similar desirable properties for quality functions for link stream partitions.

3.3.1 Property 1: Independence to Time-Aggregation Property

A common challenge in the study of temporal networks is defining a suitable time window for aggregation or determining an appropriate time granularity prior to performing dynamic community detection [11, 12, 69, 99, 100].

A notable advantage of L-Modularity is that it yields the same score for a temporal node partition on different representations of the same link-stream obtained by different time-window aggregations without loss of information, as illustrated in Fig. 3.3. This is an attractive property, expressed as follows:

Definition 3.4. A dynamic community quality function is said to be **independent to time-aggregation** if, for two representations L and L' , such as L' is obtained by aggregating L into static graphs by time intervals —multiple interactions over a period being representing by weights or multi-edges— a partition defined on L' yields the same score on L .

A significant feature of this property is that it makes L-Modularity a useful tool for comparing dynamic community structures on the same temporal network aggregated with different window sizes (see Section 3.4). In contrast, different MS-Modularity scores for community structures on the same temporal network with different aggregation window sizes are not comparable, as the multislice network changes each time.

 (a) Link stream, time granularity $\Delta_t = 1$

 (b) Link stream, time granularity $\Delta_t = 2$

 (c) Snapshots, time granularity $\Delta_t = 8$

Figure 3.3: Independence of L-Modularity to time granularity. The same interactions at the same times are shown at three aggregation scales. The L-Modularity score of the blue/red partition is identical across all three representations, since the number of internal interactions, the relative community durations, the global node degrees, and the number of affiliation discontinuities are all unchanged.

Figure 3.4: **Smoothness incentive property.** The same link stream is partitioned in two different ways, each colour representing a community. In (b), the three top nodes change communities although the network structure is unchanged. A quality function satisfying the smoothness incentive must strictly favour partition (a) over (b).

3.3.2 Property 2: Smoothness Incentive

Addressing the smoothness of temporal communities is a well-known challenge in the field of dynamic community detection [16]. We propose that a quality function for temporal community structures must explicitly promote this smoothness, as illustrated in Fig. 3.4. More formally:

Definition 3.5. Let's consider a temporal network L studied over a period T , split into two-time intervals T_1 and T_2 , and for which 1) the cumulated networks on both intervals are identical, 2) the partitions \mathcal{C}_∞ on T_1 and \mathcal{C}_ϵ on T_2 in each interval are identical. A dynamic community quality function is said to have the **smoothness incentive** if, for a partition on T , it yields a strictly higher score to a partition in which each community $C_i \in \mathcal{C}_\infty$ is merged with its corresponding community $C_i \in \mathcal{C}_\epsilon$, than to a partition in which any community in \mathcal{C}_∞ remains distinct from its equivalent one in \mathcal{C}_ϵ

3.3.3 Property 3: Topochrone Disconnection Property

In static networks, non-connected components indicate that two subsets of nodes have no links between them. Modularity assigns a higher score when non-connected components belong to different communities. In temporal networks, *disconnected topochrone components* (Def. 3.6) occur when two sub-link streams do not share any nodes nor time intervals of existence. We propose that a quality function for temporal community structures should assign a higher score when disconnected topochrone components belong to different communities, rather than the same one.

Definition 3.6. Two sub link streams L_1 and L_2 are said to be two **disconnected topochrone components** of a link stream if $T_1 \cap T_2 = V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset$.

Definition 3.7. A quality function for dynamic communities is said to respect the **topochrone disconnection** property if, given a partition in which a community contains two disconnected topochrone components, it gives a strictly higher score to the same partition in which those two topochrone components are split in two separate communities.

For example, the three communities shown in figure 3.5a in blue, green, and purple are three disconnected topochrone components. A quality function respecting the topochrone disconnection property should strictly favor partition 3.5a over 3.5b.

(a) Partition with three separate topochrone communities (favoured). (b) Partition with the two bottom topochrone components merged into one community.

Figure 3.5: **Topochrone disconnection property.** A quality function respecting this property must strictly favour partition (a) over (b). Communities are colour-coded.

3.3.4 L-Modularity and Temporal Community Properties

As discussed in Section 3.2, L-Modularity results from combinations of the inclusion or non-inclusion of the smoothness term and the choice of longitudinal expectation. We will see which combinations respect the properties.

3.3.4.1 L-Modularity and Independence to Time-Aggregation

L-Modularity is independent of time-aggregation, while MS-Modularity isn't.

This property naturally emerges from the elements used to compute L-Modularity, which depends only on the number of interactions inside communities, the time periods during which nodes belong to communities, and the total number of interactions per node.

On the contrary, MS-Modularity depends i) on the number of aggregation steps, since a higher number of snapshots leads to a higher number of inter-slice edges, encoding the smoothness term and ii) on the local degree of nodes at each step, and thus on the simultaneity of interactions, which is modified by aggregating.

It is important to note that while L-Modularity yields the same value for the same partition of the same link stream provided at multiple temporal granularities, the optimum partition might be different since a finer granularity allows to express partitions that would not be possible at coarser ones.

3.3.4.2 L-Modularity and Smoothness Incentive

The smoothness incentive property is insured by the smoothness term ρ (Eq. (3.12)), that penalizes unnecessary changes in affiliation.

3.3.4.3 L-Modularity and Topochrone Disconnection

This property is insured by the expectation term of L-Modularity. Indeed, when using \mathbb{E}_{MM} (or \mathbb{E}_{JM}), the number of edges expected inside a community grows with the time spent by nodes inside communities, even if this presence is not simultaneous. This corresponds to a vision of a perfect dynamic community as a set of nodes being homogeneously connected over a period. The topochrone disconnection goes against this objective. Note that for MS-Modularity, the situation relative to Topochrone disconnection is unclear and depends on modeling choices. If a node inactive at time t is removed completely from the network, then MS-Modularity does not fulfill the topochrone disconnection property, since no interslice edge will be added by merging the communities in a single one. If inactive nodes remain in the graph, then it respects this property, but will cause other difficulties, such as artificially rewarding the stability of communities without any observed internal edges.

3.3.5 Discussion on Temporal Communities Properties

L-Modularity values for different term combinations have been computed for all community structures shown in Figures 3.4 and 3.5. The findings are summarized in table 3.1, which illustrates which properties are promoted by the three expectations and the presence or absence of the smoothness term. The results indicate the necessity of a smoothness term to promote smoothness incentives. Additionally, it is noted that the co-membership expectation (Eq. (3.8)) does not promote robustness to topochrone disconnections. Therefore, we propose using either the joint membership expectation (Eq. (3.9)) or the mean membership expectation (Eq. (3.10)), along with the smoothness term (Eq. (3.12)).

3.4 Experimentation

In this section, we propose to evaluate L-Modularity using two different longitudinal expectations: the joint membership expectation (denoted as Q_{JM} , based on Eq.

Table 3.1: **Properties of L-Modularity variants.** Properties satisfied by each combination of longitudinal expectation (\mathbb{E}_{CM} , \mathbb{E}_{JM} , \mathbb{E}_{MM}) and smoothness term ρ , as introduced in Section 3.2.

	Independence to time aggregation	Smoothness Incentive	Robust to topochrone disconnections
\mathbb{E}_{CM}	✓	✗	✗
$\mathbb{E}_{\text{CM}} + \rho$	✓	✓	✗
\mathbb{E}_{JM}	✓	✗	✓
$\mathbb{E}_{\text{JM}} + \rho$	✓	✓	✓
\mathbb{E}_{MM}	✓	✗	✓
$\mathbb{E}_{\text{MM}} + \rho$	✓	✓	✓

(3.9)) and the mean membership (denoted as Q_{MM} , based on Eq. (3.10)), both with a smoothness weight of 2. Specifically, we use the SocioPatterns high school dataset [101], which captures the contacts and friendship relations between students at a high school in Marseilles, France, during December 2013. The interactions are recorded as 20-second interval contacts among students from nine classes over five days. The dataset also includes information on the class membership of each student.

We apply two methods to uncover dynamic community structures within the dataset. The first method involves optimizing MS-Modularity, varying the interslice weight ratio. The second method employs a no-smoothing approach [16] (later, NS-Modularity) which first applies the Louvain algorithm [7] on each snapshot and then merges successive communities based on the Jaccard Index of their node sets. We experimented the NS-Modularity method varying the minimum threshold on the Jaccard Index for two communities to merge. Ultimately, we compute the two versions of L-Modularity for each community structure obtained.

In order to use MS-Modularity and NS-Modularity, we need to perform network aggregation into snapshots. We use several steps, from days to 5-minute aggregation step. Due to computational difficulties, we were not able to perform some steps, and could not go lower than 5 minutes for MS-Modularity. Given that the data are based on interactions occurring exclusively during school hours over a span of five days, we introduce nighttime periods in our experiment. Each night begins after the final interaction of the day and ends before the first interaction of the following day. During these nighttime periods, no communities are present. Figures 3.6 and 3.7 illustrates the results.

According to both L-Modularity versions, the MS-Modularity approach yields better community structures compared to the no-smoothing method. The advantage of MS-Modularity lies in its use of interslice weights, which facilitate the direct iden-

Figure 3.6: **L-Modularity heatmaps for the SocioPatterns high school dataset.** L-Modularity scores of community structures found by MS-Modularity (MS) and the no-smoothing method (NS) under varying parameters, evaluated with Q_{MM} (top row) and Q_{JM} (bottom row).

(a) Student class membership as communities. $Q_{MM} = Q_{JM} = 0.8718$.

(b) Best structure for Q_{JM} : 157 communities, $Q_{JM} = 0.8849$.

(c) Best structure for Q_{MM} : top 12 of 48 communities shown, $Q_{MM} = 0.9019$.

(d) Structure maximising Q_{MM} without the smoothness term: 23 564 communities, $Q_{MM} = 0.98 - 2\rho$.

Figure 3.7: **Dynamic community structures in the SocioPatterns high school dataset.** Vertical black lines indicate nights during which interactions and communities cease to exist. Colours encode community membership.

tification of continuous communities. In contrast, the no-smoothing method tends to overfit individual snapshots, and this overfitting is not adequately mitigated during the merging phase. This overfitting is exacerbated by more refined window aggregations. Figures 3.6a and 3.6c illustrate the challenge of selecting appropriate window sizes and interslice weights for the MS-Modularity approach. According to L-Modularity, the finest window sizes tends to capture the most detailed temporal dynamics, and reasonably high interslice weights favor community continuity. However, determining the optimal combination of these parameters is complex. For instance, the best community structure for Q_{MM} (Fig. 3.7c) was revealed with the finest window aggregation of 5 minutes and an interslice weight ratio of 1 (MS method), which is not the highest interslice weight tested. In contrast, the best community structure for Q_{JM} was revealed with the highest interslice weight ratio of 5, and a window aggregation of 30 minutes (NS method), not the finest one. Indeed, Q_{JM} tends to favor almost stationary communities with little or no evolution over time, whereas Q_{MM} allows for more variations in dynamic community structures. Furthermore, the best community structure for Q_{JM} was revealed with the NS method by aggregating data at the scale of a day and merging successive communities from each snapshot only if they share the exact same set of nodes (Fig. 3.7b). Both versions of L-Modularity can be used depending on specific analytical needs.

One could also consider the students' classes, provided in the dataset, as a *ground truth* partition (Fig. 3.7a). This partition yields a relatively high L-Modularity score, though not the highest. The experiment indicates that some students tend to interact beyond their class affiliations. Notably, Fig. 3.7a and Fig. 3.7b share the same smoothness value, as communities are considered to last the duration of each day, with only nights contributing to the smoothness term. However, Fig. 3.7b exhibits a higher L-Modularity score, demonstrating that at the daily scale, student communities do not strictly adhere to class boundaries.

Figure 3.7d illustrates the necessity of the smoothness term. It represents the best community structure according to L-Modularity when the smoothness term is discounted.

Note that we only compared L-Modularity scores of partitions obtained by methods that do not try to optimize it directly. The best partition discovered corresponds to something close to the expected ground truth given by classes, which shows that it does not fall into common traps such as favoring partitions overfitted at each timestep. However, one could expect to discover even better longitudinal communities, such as those distinguishing class periods from lunchtime and breaks between classes. This would require an algorithm able to better explore the space of possible partitions, and this will be the object of future work.

Chapter Summary

This chapter introduced L-Modularity, a quality function that evaluates dynamic community structures directly on link streams, without requiring time aggregation. Three formally defined properties — independence to time-aggregation, smoothness incentive, and topochrone disconnection — distinguish well-behaved quality functions from degenerate ones, and L-Modularity satisfies all three when the mean-membership or joint-membership expectation is combined with the temporal smoothness term. Experiments on the SocioPatterns high school dataset confirmed that L-Modularity assigns higher scores to community structures that better reflect the underlying temporal interaction patterns.

However, a quality function alone does not enable community detection: an optimization algorithm is also required. No efficient method existed at the time of this work to explore the space of possible temporal partitions of a link stream. The next chapter addresses this limitation directly by introducing LAGO, a greedy agglomerative algorithm designed specifically to optimize L-Modularity on link streams.

Chapter 4

Optimizing L-Modularity

Chapter 3 defined L-Modularity as a quality function for dynamic communities in link streams, but a practical method also requires an algorithm to search the partition space and maximize that function. Static-graph algorithms such as Louvain [7], Leiden [49], and Infomap [98] do not extend straightforwardly to link streams, where the analog of a node — the atomic element manipulated by the algorithm — must first be defined.

This chapter — the second contribution of this thesis — introduces *LAGO* (Longitudinal Agglomerative Greedy Optimization), an algorithm that directly optimizes L-Modularity on link streams. LAGO builds on Louvain’s core principles, incorporates ideas from Leiden and Infomap, and adds components specific to the link stream setting. A novel *trimmed communities* property establishes that L-Modularity is maximized when community membership is anchored to periods of observed activity, justifying a search restricted to active time-nodes. Fourteen LAGO variants — combining three orthogonal design choices — are evaluated on synthetic and real data. This chapter is based on [22].

4.1 Definitions and notations

This section introduces the definitions and notation used throughout this chapter. Although the underlying concepts are identical to those used or introduced in the previous chapter, the notation is adapted to the specific requirements of the present chapter.

4.1.1 Link Streams

Definition 4.1. A **link stream** [14] \mathcal{L} is defined by a triplet (T, V, E) where $T \subset \mathbb{R}$ is a time interval, V a finite set of $N \in \mathbb{N}$ nodes, and $E = \{(uv, t) \in V^2 \times T\}$ a finite set of interactions.

In this chapter, we only consider the case where interactions are instantaneous, undirected, and unweighted. Also, we consider T to be discrete. It does not affect our contribution since for real-world temporal interaction data, there is a natural timestep

for a discretization that preserves exact timing which is the greatest common divisor of all the durations between successive timestamps of edges.

Let $uv_t = 1$ if $(uv, t) \in E$, else 0. We define:

$$L_{uv, T'} = \sum_{t \in T'} uv_t \quad (4.1)$$

as the number of interactions between nodes u and v over a subset of time $T' \subset T$, and $L_{uv} = L_{uv, T}$ denotes the total number of interactions between nodes u and v . Similar to static graphs, k_u denotes the degree of node u and m the total number of interactions in the link stream:

$$k_u = \sum_{v \in V} L_{uv}; \quad m = \sum_{u \in V} k_u / 2 = |E| \quad (4.2)$$

4.1.2 Temporal Communities

Definition 4.2. A dynamic community structure over a link stream is defined as a collection of non-empty and mutually exclusive communities composed of sets of node-time pairs $\{(u_1 t_1), (u_1 t_2), \dots, (u_2 t_3), (u_2 t_4), \dots\}$.

For a community C and a node u , we define:

$$T_{u \in C} = \{t \in T \text{ s.t. } ut \in C\} \quad (4.3)$$

as the set of time instants during which node u belongs to community C ,

$$T_C = \bigcup_{u \in V} T_{u \in C} \quad (4.4)$$

as the existence time of community C , and

$$L_{uv \in C} = L_{uv, T_{u \in C} \cap T_{v \in C}} \quad (4.5)$$

as the number of time edges between nodes u and v inside community C .

4.1.3 Longitudinal Modularity

As introduced and discussed in Chapter 3, the L-Modularity compares the observed fraction of interactions within communities to the expected fraction under a *longitudinal random null model*. The greater this difference, the higher the L-Modularity.

To account for the temporal dimension, two variants of L-Modularity were introduced: one based on the **Joint-Membership Expectation (JM)** and the other on the **Mean-Membership Expectation (MM)**.

Figure 4.1: **Link stream with dynamic communities.** Nodes are represented on the vertical axis; interactions occur through time.

JM (4.6) expects the overall structure of the community to be stationary or nearly stationary, with most of the nodes remaining in the same community throughout its duration.

$$\mathbb{E}_{\text{JM}} [L_{uv \in \mathcal{C}}] = \frac{k_u k_v}{2m} \frac{|T_{\mathcal{C}}|}{|T|} 1_{|T_{u \in \mathcal{C}}| |T_{v \in \mathcal{C}}| > 0} \quad (4.6)$$

MM (4.7) is more permissive, favoring more changes in node affiliations during the lifetime of a community.

$$\mathbb{E}_{\text{MM}} [L_{uv \in \mathcal{C}}] = \frac{k_u k_v}{2m} \frac{\sqrt{|T_{u \in \mathcal{C}}| |T_{v \in \mathcal{C}}|}}{|T|} \quad (4.7)$$

To quantify the temporal smoothness of dynamic communities, L-Modularity includes a regularization term based on the sum of the **Community Switch Counts** (CSC) over all nodes: $\sum \eta_u$, where η_u denotes the CSC of node u , weighted with a parameter $\omega \geq 0$.

Definition 4.3. With the previous notations, the **Longitudinal Modularity** of a dynamic community set \mathcal{C} on a link stream L regarding a time parameter $\omega > 0$ is given by:

$$Q_{\star}(L, \mathcal{C}, \omega) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{\mathcal{C} \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u, v \in V^2} [L_{uv \in \mathcal{C}} - \mathbb{E}_{\star}[L_{uv \in \mathcal{C}}]] - \frac{\omega}{2m} \sum_{u \in V} \eta_u(\mathcal{C}) \quad (4.8)$$

where $\star = JM$ or MM .

The optimization methods we propose are compatible with both versions of L-Modularity.

The term *time modules* refers to sub link streams that exhibit both temporal and topological coherence with respect to their contribution to the L-Modularity score. Strictly speaking, the optimization of L-Modularity yields time modules, which are

subsequently interpreted as dynamic communities

4.1.4 Trimmed Communities Property

Building upon the previously introduced concepts, we define the *trimmed communities property* which underpins the proposed algorithm. In essence, the property states that the L-Modularity score decreases when a community includes inactive nodes at its temporal boundaries. Consequently, communities can be trimmed to the earliest and latest active times of each of their nodes, as shown in Fig. 4.2. In other words, L-Modularity favors community memberships that are strictly anchored to periods of observed activity and penalizes artificial extensions of membership into inactive periods.

We introduce A the set of *active time nodes* consisting of time nodes that interact:

$$A = \{ut \in V \times T \mid \exists v \in V, (uv, t) \in E\} \quad (4.9)$$

which allows to consider $T_{u \in C \cap A}$ the set of time instants where node u is active inside a community C .

(a) Link stream with dynamic communities in green and blue.

(b) Trimmed version: inactive time nodes at boundaries are unaffiliated.

Figure 4.2: **Trimmed communities.** L-Modularity assigns a higher score to the trimmed community structure that starts and ends on *active time nodes* (black dots).

Definition 4.4. The *trimmed existence time of node u in community C* is

$$[T_{u \in C}] = T_{u \in C} \cap \left[\bigwedge T_{u \in C \cap A}, \bigvee T_{u \in C \cap A} \right] \quad (4.10)$$

where \bigwedge [resp. \bigvee] denotes the minimum [resp. maximum] element of a set. In other words, $[T_{u \in C}]$ is the smallest subset of $T_{u \in C}$ of all time instants between the first and last time instant where node u is active within C .

Definition 4.5. The *trimmed existence time of community C* is

$$[T_C] = \bigcup_u [T_{u \in C}] \quad (4.11)$$

Definition 4.6. The *trimmed community* $\lfloor C \rfloor$ is

$$\lfloor C \rfloor = \bigcup_{u \in V} u \times \lfloor T_{u \in C} \rfloor \quad (4.12)$$

By extension we note the set of trimmed communities as $\lfloor \mathcal{C} \rfloor = \{\lfloor C \rfloor\}_{C \in \mathcal{C}}$. Note that $T_{u \in \lfloor C \rfloor} = \lfloor T_{u \in C} \rfloor$ and $T_{\lfloor C \rfloor} = \lfloor T_C \rfloor$.

Theorem 4.7 (Trimmed Communities Property). *Let L be a link stream, \mathcal{C} a dynamic community structure on it, and $\lfloor \mathcal{C} \rfloor$ its trimmed version. Then*

$$Q_{\star}(L, \lfloor \mathcal{C} \rfloor, \omega) \geq Q_{\star}(L, \mathcal{C}, \omega) \quad (4.13)$$

where Q_{\star} denotes L -Modularity with $\star = JM$ or MM , and $\omega > 0$ is the term for time continuity constraint.

Proof. (i) The number of interactions does not change whether the time community is trimmed or not, i.e., $L_{uv \in \lfloor C \rfloor} = L_{uv \in C}$; (ii) η_u is not impacted by the durations of communities, only by their numbers, which is not impacted by trimming; (iii) longitudinal expectations have lower values in the trimmed version. Indeed, by Definition 4.4,

$$|\lfloor T_{u \in C} \rfloor| \leq |T_{u \in C}| \quad (4.14)$$

and then,

$$\mathbb{E}_{MM}[L_{uv \in \lfloor C \rfloor}] \leq \mathbb{E}_{MM}[L_{uv \in C}] \quad (4.15)$$

On the other hand, Definition 4.5 and (4.14) lead to $|\lfloor T_C \rfloor| \leq |T_C|$, meaning that,

$$\mathbb{E}_{JM}[L_{uv \in \lfloor C \rfloor}] \leq \mathbb{E}_{JM}[L_{uv \in C}] \quad (4.16)$$

□

This property implies that, with respect to L -Modularity, it is sufficient to consider only the set of active time nodes (4.9) when focusing on dynamic communities. Including other time nodes will never increase the L -Modularity value. Consequently, this reduces the amount of information that must be processed by an optimization algorithm, potentially improving computational efficiency.

4.2 Proposed Algorithm

This section details our L -Modularity optimization method, LAGO (Longitudinal Agglomerative Greedy Optimization). LAGO follows a greedy optimization approach,

inspired by existing methods developed for static networks (see Section 2.1.3.2). While preserving the general principles of these methods, we adapt the strategy to the specifics of L-Modularity and link streams.

We propose 14 LAGO variants, each corresponding to a different combination of the strategies for exploring the space of possible time modules that we introduce in this section. A summary of the variants is provided in Table 4.1.

4.2.1 Initialization step

Agglomerative methods for community detection on static networks are typically initialized with each node belonging to its own community, i.e., the finest possible partition of the network.

When temporal networks are modeled as ordered multi-slice networks—as in the multi-slice modularity[17] and Infomap adaptation to the multi-slice setting [91]—the finest scale elements are temporal nodes, i.e., a pair ut corresponding to a node u at a time t . This modeling choice results in an initialization where each ut instance is placed in its own community. Note that this is true even if the node is present but inactive.

A possible extension of this approach to link streams would consist of defining an arbitrary time step, and split the continuous lifetime of nodes accordingly, to create basic node units. One could use an arbitrary time step duration, or use the finest possible one, i.e., the greatest common divisor d of all the durations between successive timestamps of edges, ensuring no loss of temporal information. However, this leads to $|V|\frac{|T|}{d}$ elements to consider, disregarding the actual temporal activity of the network, which is often significantly sparser, thereby introducing unnecessary computational overhead.

Instead, in LAGO, we propose to focus solely on the set of active time nodes, the time nodes that interact, as defined in (4.9). According to the trimmed communities property introduced in Section 4.1.4, all information required to explore the possible dynamic communities is contained within the set of active time nodes. This property asserts that L-Modularity is maximized when nodes enter a community at the time of their first interaction within it, and exit at the time of their last interaction. So extending a node’s membership beyond its active participation leads to a reduction in the L-Modularity score. Considering time nodes with no interaction is then unnecessary.

LAGO starts by assigning each active time node to its own time module.

4.2.2 Exploration step

Greedy agglomerative approaches on static graphs rely on a local decision process for each node to update communities. Leveraging the sparsity of most real networks, one

computes node by node the profit/loss in the global objective function of switching the node from its current community to the community of each of its neighbors.

In LAGO, we need to adapt this approach to extend communities both topologically at a given time, and temporally. We thus define the set of candidate time modules for changing attribution as the topological neighbors and the temporally adjacent time modules.

In the context of link streams, reassigning an active time node ut from one time module to another involves two consequences: (i) the time segment between ut to its former module is no longer part of that module, and (ii) the time segment between ut and its new module now belongs to the new module.

4.2.2.1 Redefining the node movement operation

Contrary to the previously mentioned quality function used on static networks, L-Modularity is not *linear* in the sense defined by [102]. This implies that the impact of each local move cannot be precomputed independently of its context; it depends on the structure of the time modules involved in the move. This non-linearity arises from the expectation term, which is not linear in time: the sum of ratios is not equal to the ratio of the sums. Nevertheless, the quality function is *separable*, still in the sense of [102], meaning that the impact of a local move can be computed locally, without requiring a full recomputation of the global quality function.

As a consequence, (i) the graph aggregation phase used on static networks algorithms is not generalizable to link streams: while nodes may still be aggregated, time segments of varying durations within a time module cannot; and (ii) reassigning a sub-time module between time modules requires an evaluation of the profit/loss that involves all active time nodes involved in both the source and target time modules. This increases the computation cost of each move evaluation compared to what is done on static networks, as used in Louvain or Infomap. This underscores the importance of using fast exploration heuristic, as discussed in Section 4.2.4.

To sum up, the core algorithm, called the *Recursive Time Module Mover (RTMM)*, starts by assigning each active time node to its own time module. At any aggregation level of the algorithm, each time module is evaluated for merging with one of its neighbors: the topological neighbors and the time-adjacent modules. The move that improves the L-Modularity score the most is chosen. Note that each move trial requires (i) a computation based on all active time nodes from source and target time modules, and (ii) to compute the impact of the change of the time segments between the time modules. Figure 4.3 illustrates the first phase of the algorithm at the finest aggregation level.

Figure 4.3: **RTMM initialisation.** Each active time node (e.g. et_3) is affiliated to the community that most increases L-Modularity. Candidates are topological neighbours (e.g. dt_3) and temporally adjacent nodes (e.g. et_1, et_4). The process repeats until no move improves L-Modularity, yielding two time modules (two colours)

4.2.3 Refinement steps

As is the case for static network exploration with Louvain, only applying the core algorithm phase can lead to convergence to a poor local optimum. It is caused by the greedy merging of time modules without the ability to revisit and refine previously formed structures. We expect this issue to be further exacerbated by the addition of the temporal setting, where the optimization process must account for both topological and temporal dimensions. On static networks, refinement strategies have been proposed to overcome this limitation by enabling the reconsideration of prior decisions. We propose to adapt two such strategies, originally developed for Infomap, to the setting of link streams: (i) single-node movements, and (ii) submodule movements.

We also introduce the *Single Time Edge Movement* refinement, a modification of the single-node movements tailored for link streams.

4.2.3.1 Single Time Node Movements (STNM)

Direct generalization of the single-node movement introduced by [98] consisting in moving single active time nodes between high level aggregated time modules if it increases L-Modularity.

4.2.3.2 Sub Time Modules Movements (STMM)

Direct generalization of the submodules movement introduced by [98] consisting in recomputing local submodules with RTMM solely on the induced sub link stream, and allowing them to change time module affiliation if it increases L-Modularity.

4.2.3.3 Single Time Edge Movements (STEM)

This strategy generalizes Single Time Node Movements by allowing two interacting time nodes in the same community to be moved simultaneously. This joint movement addresses an expected limitation of independent node movements along the time axis: when attempting to reassign two connected active time nodes sequentially, the first move may result in a temporarily decrease in L-Modularity. This occurs because moving time nodes one by one temporarily extends the presence in a time module without contributing additional internal interaction, thereby increasing the expected number of interaction without a corresponding topological gain. By contrast, moving the two interacting time nodes together preserves their topological contribution to the community and lead to an L-Modularity increase. To ensure that the benefits of individual time nodes exploration are not lost, the STEM strategy also incorporates the STNM strategy.

4.2.4 Substitutions

Other approaches have been proposed to improve greedy agglomerative optimization algorithms. In this section, we present two such substitutions, both incorporated into LAGO, which modify the application of either the core algorithm or its refinement phases.

4.2.4.1 Fast Exploration (FE)

In the first phase of the Time Module Mover, iterating over all candidates time module and computing potential moves to neighbors implies a lot of computation with no guarantee of success. Moreover, the process starts again whenever at least one move in the list improves the quality function. As discussed in Section 4.2.2.1, evaluating the impact of a move requires recomputing the contribution of all active time nodes in both the source and target time modules. In order to reduce the number of unnecessary computations we propose to adapt the efficient exploration strategy used in the Leiden algorithm[49]. We call it the Fast Exploration (FE). It is a heuristic that reduces the number of candidate neighbors to evaluate. The principle is to maintain a limited set of candidates, updated at each time module affiliation change. For each successful move, the neighbors of the moved time modules are added to the set of candidates.

At each step, a candidate is selected and removed from the set for evaluation. The process continues until the set is empty, enabling localized but adaptive exploration of the solution space, while significantly reducing unnecessary computations.

4.2.4.2 Refinement In RTMM (RIR)

In the context of static networks, refinement strategies are applied either after the main optimization loop [98] or within it [49]. Intuitively, applying refinement post hoc tends to result in faster algorithms, while incorporating it during the main loop may yield more fine-grained community structures. In this chapter, we propose to compare the performance of both approaches when adapted to the context of link streams.

Table 4.1: LAGO variants. We consider 14 greedy algorithms, each representing a different combination of the steps introduced in this section. While all variants share the same foundational method –RTMM (Section 4.2.2.1)–they differ in the specific refinements (Section 4.2.3) and substitutions (Section 4.2.4) applied.

Methods	Core	Refinement			Substitution	
	RTMM 4.2.2.1	<i>STNM</i> 4.2.3.1	<i>STMM</i> 4.2.3.2	<i>STEM</i> 4.2.3.3	<i>FE</i> 4.2.4.1	<i>RIR</i> 4.2.4.2
<i>LV</i>	v					
<i>LV</i> ★	v				v	
<i>IM</i> + <i>N</i>	v	v	v			
<i>IM</i> + <i>N</i> ★	v	v	v		v	
<i>IM</i> + <i>E</i>	v		v	v		
<i>IM</i> + <i>E</i> ★	v		v	v	v	
<i>LV</i> × <i>N</i>	v	v				v
<i>LV</i> × <i>N</i> ★	v	v			v	v
<i>LV</i> × <i>E</i>	v			v		v
<i>LV</i> × <i>E</i> ★	v			v	v	v
<i>LV</i> + <i>N</i>	v	v				
<i>LV</i> + <i>N</i> ★	v	v			v	
<i>LV</i> + <i>E</i>	v			v		
<i>LV</i> + <i>E</i> ★	v			v	v	

4.3 Experiments

In this section, we demonstrate that LAGO is successful for optimizing L-Modularity, enabling the discovery of meaningful dynamic communities in link streams. We evaluate the different variants of LAGO (Table 4.1) with respect to scalability, optimization performance, and their ability to recover ground truth communities. Experiments are conducted on both synthetic and real-world temporal networks. Notably, a direct

comparison with existing approaches is not possible, as no prior method has been proposed for the optimization of L-Modularity. Moreover, as highlighted by the authors of L-Modularity [21], no publicly available method currently supports community detection directly on link streams. Our evaluation therefore focuses on comparing the performance of the different LAGO variants.

4.3.1 Synthetic Dataset, Custom Community Structure

Figure 4.4: **LAGO performance on synthetic data.** Performance of LAGO variants in recovering the ground truth community structure (Fig. 4.4a) across different link stream sizes. Both versions of L-Modularity are optimized. The following metrics are reported: time of execution, final L-Modularity values, and the accuracy of community recovery as measured by the Normalized Variation of Information (NVI) between the detected and ground truth communities. The size of a link stream is the number of its active time nodes.

The first experiment demonstrates that LAGO is successful in recovering unambiguously defined dynamic communities. It also assesses its scalability.

To conduct this evaluation, we use a generator of dynamic networks with planted community structures. While various methods exist in the literature, such as [16, 103], we use the *mosaic* benchmark framework introduced by Asgari et al. [104], because it allows the generation of sparse link streams, and not slowly evolving graphs.

We first define a simple dynamic community structure illustrated in Fig. 4.4a. Link streams are then generated by varying both the number of nodes and the maximum number of timesteps, proportionally scaling the community structure. Temporal edges

are generated using the parameters from the benchmark framework, with an internal density coefficient $\alpha = 0.8$, and a community identifiability coefficient $\beta = 0$, indicating the absence of interactions between nodes belonging to different communities.

We argue that an effective method for dynamic community detection should be capable of recovering these simple and well-defined dynamic communities.

Figure 4.4 shows that LAGO successfully recovers the ground truth communities. This is evidenced by the high L-Modularity values—closely matching those of the ground truth—and the low Normalized Variation of Information (NVI) scores. Interestingly, optimizing Q_{MM} yields better performance than optimizing Q_{JM} , despite the ground truth structure being more naturally aligned with the assumptions underlying Q_{JM} . We hypothesize that this is due to the more restrictive nature of Q_{JM} , which may lead the optimization to become trapped in local optima.

Regardless of the LAGO variant used to optimize Q_{JM} , the results suggest that beyond a certain link stream size, the optimization process tends to a plateau, likely becoming trapped in suboptimal configurations. In contrast, optimization of Q_{MM} appears more stable, achieving consistent performance across different link stream sizes.

Overall, the best-performing LAGO variant in this experiment, for both versions of L-Modularity, is $LV + E\star$. It consistently ranks among the top in terms of final L-Modularity values while also being the second fastest in execution time.

4.3.2 Synthetic Dataset, Random Partitions

The exploration of the space of possible temporal communities is influenced by numerous factors that remain largely underexplored. These include the number of nodes, the number of time steps, their ratio, the density of temporal interactions and their variations, as well as the choice of quality function, its parameters, and the associated optimization strategy. Furthermore, there is currently no universally accepted definition of what constitutes a “good” dynamic community. To prevent evaluation bias, we avoid relying exclusively on arbitrarily predefined community structures when evaluating LAGO.

To address these limitations, we evaluate LAGO’s performance across a broad spectrum of synthetic link streams and dynamic community structures, randomly generated. We adopt a relative performance approach, comparing the 14 LAGO variants on a diverse set of generated link streams to identify performance trends. For each instance, the variants are ranked independently on two criteria: (i) execution time, and (ii) the final value of the optimized L-Modularity. Rankings are assigned from best (rank 1) to worst (rank 14) per criterion.

The synthetic link streams are generated using the framework proposed by Asgari et al. [104]. Parameters are sampled uniformly: the number of nodes between 25 and 250;

the maximum number of timesteps between 50 and 250; the internal density coefficient α between 0.5 and 1; and the inter-community interaction coefficient β between 0 and 0.5, subject to the constraint $\beta < \alpha/3$ to ensure clearly separable communities. Each LAGO variant is executed three times per link stream, and only the median values are retained for evaluation. It enables more reliable results since the greedy methods are based on randomness. The average size of the generated link streams is 10,122 active time nodes, with a standard deviation of 8,468.

Figure 4.5 presents the comparative results of the LAGO variants. We can observe a Pareto front of optimality composed of very few methods, with those in the bottom left dominating most others. For both L-Modularity objectives, LV and $LV\star$ consistently achieve the fastest execution times but yield the lowest L-Modularity scores. This highlights the importance of incorporating a refinement phase in the algorithm, as these two variants are the only ones with no such incorporated step.

Furthermore, variants without the Fast Exploration option tend to be slower, with the notable exception of $IM + N\star$ and $IM + E\star$, both of which incorporate STMM. STMM is computationally expensive due to the non-linearity [102] of L-Modularity and requires considering all active time nodes involved in a move—of both source and target module—to compute the related improvement.

Interestingly, incorporating Fast Exploration does not degrade optimization performance. On the contrary, LAGO variants that include this strategy generally outperform those that do not. This supports the hypothesis that prioritizing the neighbors of previously moved time modules is a more effective exploration strategy than random selection.

Additionally, LAGO variants that incorporate the "Refinement In RTMM" mechanism generally exhibit longer execution times compared to their counterparts without this mechanism. This is consistent with the increased number of loop iterations and candidate evaluations required by the refinement process.

Among LAGO variants, $LV \times N\star$ achieves the best results for optimizing Q_{JM} , while $LV \times E\star$ performs best for Q_{MM} . Nevertheless, both variants demonstrate strong performance across both objective functions. The inclusion of the STEM mechanism appears particularly advantageous for Q_{MM} , while STNM is more effective for Q_{JM} . This may be explained by the fact that in Q_{JM} , even a slight extension of a node's membership duration in a community directly influences the community's total duration and thus its contribution to the L-Modularity score.

In conclusion, this experiment reveals that more exhaustive move trials do not necessarily lead to better optimization outcomes; on the contrary, excessive exploration may increase the risk of becoming trapped in poor local optima. The STMM mechanism appears to be significantly less effective and could be excluded from future configurations. All effective variants include Fast Exploration, underscoring its practi-

(a) Performances distributions of LAGO optimizing Q_{JM} .

(b) Performances distributions of LAGO optimizing Q_{MM} .

Figure 4.5: **Relative performance of LAGO variants.** For each variant, the cross marks the mean rank on execution time and L-Modularity value; boxes span the 1st-3rd quartile; whiskers extend to the 1st-9th decile. Best variants appear in the bottom-left corner.

cal value. The final choice between LAGO flavors should depend on specific use-case requirements.

4.3.3 Real Data Application

(a) Dynamic communities obtained with LAGO.

(b) Dynamic communities obtained by Multi Slice Modularity optimisation.

Figure 4.6: **Dynamic communities in the Primary School SocioPatterns dataset.** Students are shown as horizontal lines; curved lines indicate face-to-face interactions. Colours show the communities visited by the highlighted student (bold, arrowhead); all others are grey.

In this section, we evaluate LAGO on real-world temporal data and compare its performance with the closest existing method for dynamic community detection based on modularity: multislice modularity [17], an extension of modularity designed to detect dynamic communities in temporal networks represented as sequences of static networks.

We use the primary school socio-pattern dataset [8], which records interactions between pairs of students every 20 seconds when they face each other. The dataset also includes class membership information for each student. It allows for observing

the dynamics of interactions over few days with different phases alternating between lectures and breaks.

In the absence of reliable ground truth, performance is assessed qualitatively through visualization of the link stream and detected dynamic communities. Due to limitations imposed by the size of the dataset, both in terms of the number of nodes and the number of time steps, we focus on interactions among three classes during the first day of recording. This subset contains 72 students, 1,555 time steps, and 28,904 active time nodes.

We apply the $LV \times N$ variant of LAGO to optimize Q_{JM} , with a temporal smoothing parameter $\omega = 15$ on the link stream. We compare it with multislice modularity, using an existing implementation¹. We chose the weights parameters in order to produce a manageable number of communities for interpretation.

The results are shown in Figure 4.6. The figure uses a standard approach to visualize temporal networks[105], with nodes represented as horizontal lines and interactions as vertical lines, allowing to identify dense periods of interactions between subsets of nodes. The visualization focuses on a single student, highlighted with a bold horizontal black line. Colored communities are those in which the student belongs during at least one time step. LAGO identifies 11 dynamic communities for this student. The first three communities visited by the student—colored red, orange, and pink—primarily consist of classmates, though with varying patterns of affiliation. Each community lasts approximately one hour, matching the duration of a lecture in that school. Similarly, the last three communities (green, purple, and magenta) reflect different interactions with students from the same class. During the lunch break, the student visits five communities, each comprising different subsets of students from all the classes.

In contrast, the communities detected by the multislice modularity method (Figure 4.6b) appear less meaningful. This is unsurprising, as the multislice approach was not designed to handle rapid interactions and frequent changes characteristic of this dataset.

It is worth noting that the multislice approach treats the link stream as a sequence of snapshots, requiring consideration of $|V| \times |T| = 72 \times 1555 = 111960$ time nodes. By contrast, LAGO only considers 28904 active time nodes, leading to more efficient computation.

4.3.4 Results Highlights

Experiments demonstrate that LAGO effectively optimizes L-Modularity, though its efficiency varies with the choice of variant. Performance depends on both the target objective— Q_{JM} or Q_{MM} —and the structure of the link stream. This is illustrated by

¹<https://github.com/vtraag/leidenalg>

the first two experiments, ranging from simple (Section 4.3.1) to complex, randomly generated link streams (Section 4.3.2), and do not consistently favor the same LAGO variants for optimal performance. Nevertheless, the experiments suggest general guidelines for effective LAGO use:

- **Refinement strategy:** Strongly recommended. While STNM generally yields better performance for Q_{JM} and STEM for Q_{MM} , this association is not absolute and may vary depending on the context. The use of STMM is not recommended.
- **Fast Exploration:** Strongly recommended. This mechanism significantly reduces computation time and improves L-Modularity scores.
- **Refinement in RTMM:** Optional. It tends to improve results but increases computational cost.

Chapter Summary

This chapter introduced LAGO, the first algorithm designed to optimize L-Modularity directly on link streams. By establishing the trimmed communities property, the search is reduced to the *active time nodes* — the node–time pairs that actually participate in interactions. It avoids the computational overhead of considering inactive time nodes while remaining guaranteed not to miss any partition that would improve L-Modularity.

The experimental evaluation across synthetic and real data leads to three consistent practical recommendations. Fast Exploration should always be enabled: it reduces computation time and, counter to intuition, also improves the quality of the final partition by focusing exploration on the most productive local neighbourhood. STMM should be avoided, as its computational cost is not matched by quality gains. The choice between STNM and STEM depends on the target objective: STNM is more effective for Q_{JM} , while STEM better suits Q_{MM} . These associations reflect the different sensitivity of each objective to extensions of node membership duration. The application to the SocioPatterns primary school dataset demonstrated that LAGO recovers interpretable community structures aligned with known school schedules.

Taken together, Chapters 3 and 4 constitute a complete framework for community detection in simple instantaneous link streams: a quality function and an algorithm to optimize it. However, both were developed under the assumption that interactions are instantaneous, undirected, unweighted, and occur between nodes of a single type. Real-world temporal datasets rarely satisfy all of these constraints. Financial transaction networks are directed and weighted; contact networks may record sustained co-presence rather than instantaneous events; transportation systems exhibit delays between departure and arrival; recommendation systems involve heterogeneous node

types. The following chapter extends the framework to this broader and more realistic class of networks.

Chapter 5

Extensions Beyond Simple Temporal Networks

Chapters 3 and 4 established L-Modularity as a quality function and LAGO as its optimizer for community detection in link streams, but both assume *simple* link streams: undirected, unweighted, single-class nodes, and instantaneous interactions. Real data routinely breaks these assumptions — financial transactions are weighted and directed, bike-sharing trips occupy continuous intervals with departure-to-arrival delay, and online platforms link users to hashtags in bipartite form.

This chapter — the third contribution of this thesis — removes the simplicity assumption by introducing *generalized link streams*, a unified formalism that accommodates weighted, directed, continuous, delayed, and multipartite interactions, and extends both L-Modularity and LAGO to this setting. The quality function gains a resolution parameter — as in static modularity — controlling community granularity, and active time-nodes generalize to active time-segment nodes. The framework is validated on three datasets targeting distinct dimensions: the Eurovision voting network (directed, weighted), Citi Bike trips (interval-based, delayed), and Bluesky (bipartite). This chapter is based on [23].

5.1 Generalizing Link Streams

As discussed in Section 2.2.3, *Link streams* model temporal interactions as series of triplets (u, v, t) , each representing an *interaction* between nodes u and v at time t . These interactions are typically assumed to be instantaneous.

In this section, we introduce the concept and definition of *generalized link stream*, mainly inspired by [14, 76], which will be used throughout the chapter. Although this definition does not cover all possible variants of link streams, we adopt the term *generalized link stream* in contrast to what we call *simple link streams*, on which the original L-Modularity is defined.

Real-world temporal data often involve richer interaction mechanisms, including **weights**, **directions**, or **multipartite** node structures. For example, financial trans-

actions are often modeled as having a *sender* (source), sending some *amount* to a *receiver* (destination) at a particular time; online social networks may record events as having a *user* associated with a *hashtag* at a specific time. Weights, directionality and heterogeneity of nodes have already been widely studied in the literature on static networks; we will extend these works to link streams.

In generalized link streams, we will also introduce additional interaction modalities that are specific to the temporal setting. Indeed, interactions may be instantaneous (e.g., sending an email), may persist over a time interval (e.g., phone calls), or may involve delays between departure and arrival (e.g., transportation systems). An **instantaneous interaction** occurs at a single time t and corresponds to the classical link stream event (u, v, t) . A **continuous interaction** persists over a time interval $[t_s, t_e)$ and naturally represents sustained phenomena such as co-location or ongoing communication. Such an interaction is denoted (u, v, t_s, t_e) . Many systems involve **delayed interactions**, where an interaction departs from node u at time t_s and reaches node v at a later time t_d , for example airplane flights or shipments in supply chains. These interactions are denoted (u, v, t_s, t_d) .

Instantaneous interactions correspond to the special case $t_s = t_d$. We refer to both instantaneous and delayed interactions collectively as **timestamp-based interactions** (since each is fully characterized by one or two discrete timestamps), as opposed to **interval-based interactions** corresponding to continuous interactions. We adopt this terminology to avoid ambiguity with the continuous or discrete nature of the time domain of the network.

5.1.1 Definition of a Generalized Link Stream

In this section, we define the generalized link stream, of which the simple link stream is a particular case.

Definition 5.1. A **link stream** is defined as

$$L = (T, V, E),$$

where $T \subset \mathbb{R}$ (resp. $T \subset \mathbb{Z}$) is a continuous (resp. discrete) time interval, V is a finite set of nodes, and E is a finite set of temporal interactions.

Each interaction is **directed**, with the ordered pair (u, v) encoding the direction from node u to node v , and carries a **weight** $w \in \mathbb{R}_+$, assumed to be 1 when not specified. Undirected interactions are treated as two reciprocal directed interactions.

Depending on the temporal nature of the interactions, the edge set E takes one of two forms.

Timestamp-based interactions

$$E = \{(u, v, t_s, t_d, w) \in V^2 \times T^2 \times \mathbb{R}_+ : t_s \leq t_d\}, \quad (5.1)$$

where t_s and t_d denote the departure time from node u and the arrival time at node v , respectively. Instantaneous interactions correspond to the special case $t_s = t_d$. We refer to both instantaneous and delayed interactions collectively as **timestamp-based interactions**.

Interval-based interactions

$$E = \{(u, v, t_s, t_e, w) \in V^2 \times T^2 \times \mathbb{R}_+ : t_s \leq t_e\}, \quad (5.2)$$

where $[t_s, t_e)$ is the time interval during which the interaction persists. This corresponds to what was earlier referred to as continuous interactions.

We adopt the terms timestamp-based and interval-based to avoid ambiguity with the continuous or discrete nature of the time domain T . A given link stream is assumed to contain exclusively one type or the other.

Multipartite link streams When the network is **multipartite**, the node set is written

$$V = \bigcup_{i=1}^P V_i,$$

where $\{V_i\}_i^P$ is a partition of V . Interactions are only allowed between different parts, i.e. $u, v \in V_i \Rightarrow (u, v, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot) \notin E$. When $P = 2$, the link stream is said to be bipartite.

5.1.2 Generalizing Useful Definitions on Link Streams

To redefine the L-Modularity over a generalized link stream, we need to introduce some notations common to the different types of generalizations.

5.1.2.1 Interactions Over a Period

Timestamp-based interactions We define

$$I_{uv, T' T''} = \{(u, v, t_s, t_d, w) \in E \text{ such that } (t_s, t_d) \in T' \times T''\}$$

the set of interactions leaving u during the period T' and arriving at v during the period T'' . The **number** of interactions L , and the **total weight** of interactions W

are defined respectively as

$$L_{uv,T'T''} = |I_{uv,T'T''}|, \quad W_{uv,T'T''} = \sum_{\substack{(u,v,t_s,t_d,w) \\ \in I_{uv,T'T''}}} w.$$

For **instantaneous interactions**, we simply write

$$I_{uv,T'} = I_{uv,T'T'}, \quad L_{uv,T'} = L_{uv,T'T'}, \quad \text{and} \quad W_{uv,T'} = W_{uv,T'T'}.$$

Interval-based interactions We define the instantaneous interaction intensity

$$uv_t = \sum_{\substack{(u,v,t_s,t_e,w) \in E \\ t_s \leq t < t_e}} w,$$

which represents the total weight of interactions from u to v at time t . The **total weight** of interactions from u to v over an interval $T' \subseteq T$ is

$$W_{uv,T'} = \int_{t \in T'} uv_t dt \quad \text{if } T \subset \mathbb{R}, \quad W_{uv,T'} = \sum_{t \in T'} uv_t \quad \text{if } T \subset \mathbb{Z}.$$

General setting In both timestamp-based and interval-based settings we denote the **total interaction weight** from u to v over the whole observation period as

$$W_{uv} = W_{uv,T}.$$

Figure 5.1 illustrates both timestamp-based and interval-based link streams with examples of the notations introduced in this section.

Figure 5.1: **Link stream representations.** Interactions are unweighted and undirected over the node set $V = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$. Nodes are shown on the vertical axis and time T on the horizontal axis. **Panel (a):** 13 interactions, including both instantaneous and delayed events, e.g., $W_{ce,T'} = 1$ and $W_{ce} = 2$. **Panel (b):** 8 interactions; durations are represented as horizontal segments; for example, $ab_{t_2} = 1$, $bd_{t_1} = 0$, and $W_{ac,[t_1,t_4]} = t_4 - t_3$.

5.1.2.2 Total In-Out Degrees

To define the null model of L-Modularity, we need to use the total degree of nodes over the whole period of the link stream. Similarly to directed weighted graphs in the static setting, the in- and out-degrees are defined as

$$k_u^{\text{in}} = \sum_{v \in V} W_{vu}, \quad k_u^{\text{out}} = \sum_{v \in V} W_{uv}.$$

Finally, the total weight of the link stream is

$$w = \sum_{u \in V} k_u^{\text{in}} = \sum_{u \in V} k_u^{\text{out}} = \sum_{uv \in V^2} W_{uv},$$

and the number of interactions is $m = |E|$.

We consider that interactions in undirected link streams should be equivalent to having directed interactions in both directions. As a consequence, we have

$$k_u = k_u^{\text{in}} = k_u^{\text{out}}, \quad w = \sum_{u \in V} k_u,$$

respectively the undirected degree of node u and the weight of the network. In the unweighted and undirected case, $w = 2|E| = 2m$.

These notations allow to express all concepts used in the following sections, regardless of whether T is continuous or discrete, and independently of the interaction temporal type (timestamp-based or interval-based) or additional features introduced above.

5.2 L-Modularity Beyond Simple Link Streams

In this section, we extend L-Modularity beyond simple instantaneous link streams (Sec. 5.2.3). We first specify the notion of dynamic communities considered in this chapter (Sec. 5.2.1), and then recall the original definition of L-Modularity (Sec. 5.2.2).

5.2.1 Dynamic Communities

This section introduces the definitions and notation used throughout this chapter. Although the underlying concepts closely follow those introduced in previous chapters, the notation is adapted to the specific requirements of the present chapter and extended with additional concepts.

Definition 5.2. Let $L = (T, V, E)$ be a general link stream. A **dynamic community structure** over L is defined as a collection of **non-empty** and **mutually exclusive**

communities composed of sets of node–time-segment pairs

$$\{(u_1, [t_1, t'_1]), (u_2, [t_2, t'_2]), \dots, (u_2, [t''_2, t'''_2]), (u_3, [t_3, t'_3]), \dots\}$$

such that, for any node u , the time segments associated with u do not overlap. This definition is compatible with both discrete and continuous time domains T and any type of interactions E .

We introduce the following notations. For a node u and a community C ,

$$T_{u \in C} = \bigcup_{(u, [t_i, t_{i+1})) \in C} [t_i, t_{i+1})$$

denotes the set of times during which node u belongs to community C .

$$L_{uv \in C} = L_{uv, T_{u \in C} T_{v \in C}}, \quad W_{uv \in C} = W_{uv, T_{u \in C} T_{v \in C}}$$

denote respectively the number of interactions (for timestamp-based link streams only) and the cumulative weight of interactions from node u to node v occurring while both nodes belong to community C .

$$T_C = \bigcup_{u \in V} T_{u \in C}$$

denotes the existence time of community C .

5.2.2 L-Modularity for Simple Temporal Networks

To evaluate the quality of dynamic communities in simple instantaneous link streams, Chapter 3 introduced longitudinal modularity (L-modularity). We recall here the definitions using notation adapted to the present chapter.

The expected number of interactions $\mathbb{E}_\star [L_{uv \in C}]$ between nodes u and v within a dynamic community C is obtained by weighting the configuration null model of the static setting by a temporal factor:

$$\mathbb{E}_\star [L_{uv \in C}] = \frac{k_u k_v}{2m} \mathbb{T}_{uv, C}^\star, \quad (5.3)$$

where $\mathbb{T}_{uv, C}^\star$ correspond to two variants of longitudinal random null model: the **Joint-Membership (JM)** and the **Mean-Membership (MM)**.

JM (5.4) expects the overall structure of the community to be stationary or nearly stationary, meaning that most nodes remain in the same community throughout its

lifetime:

$$\mathbb{T}_{uv,C}^{\text{JM}} = \frac{|T_C|}{|T|} \mathbf{1}_{|T_{u \in C}| |T_{v \in C}| > 0}. \quad (5.4)$$

In contrast, the MM formulation (5.5) is more permissive and allows more frequent changes in node affiliations during the lifetime of a community:

$$\mathbb{T}_{uv,C}^{\text{MM}} = \frac{\sqrt{|T_{u \in C}| |T_{v \in C}|}}{|T|}. \quad (5.5)$$

L-Modularity also includes a temporal regularization term that quantifies the temporal smoothness of dynamic community structure. This term is based on the sum of the **Community Switch Count** (CSC) over all nodes, $\sum \eta_u$, where η_u denotes the CSC of node u . The CSC measures how frequently a node changes its community membership over time. Specifically, η_u is the number of communities visited by node u minus one, and zero if the node never leaves a community.

The regularization term is weighted by a parameter $\omega \geq 0$, which controls the temporal smoothness. When $\omega = 0$, L-Modularity favors communities with instantaneous lifetimes. Larger values of ω encourage temporal stability in node memberships.

Finally, the L-Modularity formulation of a dynamic community set \mathcal{C} on a simple link stream $L = (T, V, E)$ is

$$Q_{\star}(L, \mathcal{C}, \omega) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u,v \in V^2} \left[L_{uv \in C} - \frac{k_u k_v}{2m} \mathbb{T}_{uv,C}^{\star} \right] - \frac{\omega}{2m} \sum_{u \in V} \eta_u(\mathcal{C}), \quad (5.6)$$

where $\star = \text{JM}$ or MM , and $\omega \geq 0$ a time smoothness parameter.

5.2.3 L-Modularity Beyond Simple Temporal Networks

We extend L-Modularity to evaluate dynamic community structures in temporal networks that may be weighted, directed, continuous, delayed, or defined over multipartite node sets. To our knowledge, this constitutes the first quality function designed to evaluate dynamic community structures in such general temporal network settings. The section first discusses the main components of L-Modularity affected by this generalization, then introduces the formal definition, and finally discusses the role of meta-parameters as well as the choice of null model with respect to the different types of interactions.

5.2.3.1 Conceptual Components

The function relies on three key components: (i) the observed interactions within communities; (ii) the expected amount of interactions under a null model; and (iii) a temporal regularization term ensuring temporal smoothness of the community structure.

Observed interactions As defined in the last section, the observed weight of interactions from node u to node v within community C is given by $W_{uv \in C}$. The term encapsulates weighted and directed interactions, is independent of whether the node set is unipartite or multipartite, and is compatible with both timestamp-based and interval-based interactions.

Expected interactions We generalize the expectation term by extending the configuration null model used in static modularity [6] to settings that allow weighted, directed, and multipartite networks. Such generalizations are well established in the static case and rely on replacing node degrees with appropriate in/out strengths [58] and restricting interactions according to node types [59]. We adopt these extensions while preserving the temporal component of the longitudinal null model. The expected weight of interactions from node u to node v within community C is defined as

$$\mathbb{E}_\star [W_{uv \in C}] = b_{uv} \frac{k_u^{\text{out}} k_v^{\text{in}}}{w} \mathbb{T}_{uv, C}^\star, \quad (5.7)$$

where $\star = \text{JM}$ or MM and $b_{uv} = 1$ if interactions between nodes u and v are allowed (i.e., compatible types in multipartite networks) and 0 otherwise. In unipartite networks, $b_{uv} \equiv 1$. In the quality function (Definition 5.3), this expectation is scaled by a resolution parameter $\gamma > 0$, following the static setting [51], that controls the granularity of detected communities.

In this formulation, certain link stream features are explicit — such as multipartite constraints and interaction directionality — while others, including interaction weights and whether interactions are interval-based or timestamp-based, are incorporated implicitly through the aggregated quantities.

For multipartite structures, no interactions are expected between nodes of the same kind and the weight of interactions expected between nodes of different kind is equivalent to the unipartite case.

For directed networks, the expected weight of interactions from u to v is proportional to the out-strength of u (k_u^{out}) and the in-strength of v (k_v^{in}).

Note that the expected weight of interaction does not depend on the temporal distribution of the interactions themselves. The null model only incorporates temporal information through the longitudinal factor $\mathbb{T}_{uv, C}^\star$, which reflects the co-membership of

nodes in a community over time.

Consequently, two interaction patterns with the same total interaction weight over a given time interval have the same expectation under the null model. For instance, two continuous interactions of duration d are equally expected as a single interaction of duration $2d$. Similarly, five instantaneous interactions of weight 1 have the same expectation as one interaction of weight 5. Temporal concentration of interactions therefore appears as statistically surprising relative to the null model, potentially revealing communities.

The framework is adaptable to alternative null models tailored to specific datasets or objectives.

Temporal smoothness The temporal regularization term penalizes frequent community switches. In the original formulation, for simple instantaneous interactions, it is normalized by $2m$, which approximates the number of time nodes involved in interactions: each interaction contributes two endpoints. This normalization prevents degenerate configurations where each interacting time node forms a separate community, which would drive the expectation term to zero and artificially maximize L-Modularity.

A natural question is whether this normalization should depend on the nature of interactions in the temporal network.

We adopt the principle that the counting of community switches should remain independent of the structural complexity of the link stream. In other words, the regularization term should reflect only the frequency of switches, and not be biased by how interactions are encoded.

Directed, delayed, and multipartite temporal networks do not require a modification of the temporal regularization term, as they do not alter the definition of instantaneous time nodes or community switches; consequently, the normalization by $2m$ remains unchanged.

In the weighted setting, one may wish to penalize community switches proportionally to the weights of the interactions involved. For instance, switches associated with low-weight interactions could be considered less significant, whereas switches affecting high-weight interactions would have a stronger impact on the desired temporal smoothness of communities. However, incorporating such refinements would require a substantial reformulation of the regularization term, which we leave for future work.

In the interval-based setting, although interactions are not represented as time-tamped events, the regularization should still be normalized by an approximation of the number of time nodes are involved in interactions. In this context, $2m$ (i.e., twice the number of interactions) remains a convenient proxy. This choice ensures that the regularization term is comparable across different temporal representations while preserving its role in preventing degenerate solutions.

5.2.3.2 Formal Definition

Definition 5.3. Let $L = (T, V, E)$ be a general link stream. With the previous notations, the **general Longitudinal Modularity** of a dynamic community set \mathcal{C} regarding a resolution parameter $\gamma > 0$ and time parameter $\omega \geq 0$ is given by:

$$Q_{\star}(L, \mathcal{C}, \gamma, \omega) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{u, v \in V^2} \left[W_{uv \in C} - \gamma b_{uv} \frac{k_u^{\text{out}} k_v^{\text{in}}}{w} \mathbb{T}_{uv, C}^{\star} \right] - \frac{\omega}{2m} \sum_{u \in V} \eta_u(\mathcal{C}), \quad (5.8)$$

where $\star = \text{JM or MM}$. $b_{uv} = 1$ if nodes u and v belong to different types and $b_{uv} = 0$ otherwise. When unipartite, $b_{uv} \equiv 1$. When the network is unweighted and undirected, $w = 2m$, and $W_{uv \in C}$ reduces to the number of interactions $L_{uv \in C}$ if interactions are discrete. For undirected networks, each interaction can be treated as two reciprocal directed interactions, so that $k_u = k_u^{\text{in}} = k_u^{\text{out}}$.

5.2.3.3 Meta-Parameters Influence

The resolution parameter γ controls the expected density of interactions within communities. Lower values favor larger, less dense communities, while higher values favor smaller, denser ones. The temporal penalty ω regulates community stability over time: lower values allow frequent community changes, while higher values encourage temporally stable partitions.

Figure 5.2 illustrates these effects on a simple instantaneous link stream. Panels show how different combinations of (γ, ω) influence the size and temporal smoothness of detected communities.

5.2.3.4 Impacts of Interactions Types and Longitudinal Null Model

The choice of temporal variant in the longitudinal null model directly affects the expected temporal shape of communities. The Joint-Membership (JM) expectation (5.4) assumes that the overall community structure is stationary or nearly stationary: the expected amount of interaction is proportional to the total duration of the community, disregarding the specific times nodes are present in the community. In contrast, the Mean-Membership (MM) expectation (5.5) accounts for the effective time a node spends in a community, allowing more flexible temporal patterns.

This distinction is particularly critical in link streams with delayed interactions. Under JM, a node may be considered part of a community as soon as an interaction *targeted to it* begins, even if the node is not yet effectively engaged in the interaction. MM, on the other hand, only accounts for the time during which the node is actually involved, leading to different temporal community assignments.

Figure 5.2: **Impact of γ and ω on temporal community structure.** Different community structures are shown in colors on a simple link stream, favored by different resolution parameters γ and time smoothness terms ω . Lower γ favors fewer communities, and lower ω favors more changes over time.

Figure 5.3 illustrates these differences on a simple delayed link stream. In particular, (a) and (b) show two alternative community structures on the same temporal network: one better aligned with MM, favoring temporally localized memberships, and the other with JM, favoring more persistent communities. Although both partitions are evaluated using the same quality function (L-Modularity), their scores differ depending on the null model: MM favors (a), whereas JM favors (b).

Additionally, (c) and (d) illustrates on a toy example how different modeling choices for delayed interactions (instantaneous vs. interval-based representations) can alter the temporal structure of the network. These representations reduce the discrepancy between JM and MM, yielding community structures that are simultaneously favored by both null models.

Overall, this example highlights that both the interaction model and the longitudinal null model jointly shape the detected temporal communities, with particularly strong effects in the presence of delayed interactions, emphasizing the importance of accurately modeling real-world data.

5.3 Dynamic Community Detection: LAGO

LAGO (Longitudinal Agglomerative Greedy Optimization) has been introduced in [22] to optimize L-Modularity on simple instantaneous link streams, and thereby uncover

Figure 5.3: **Four representations of a link stream with different interaction models and community structures.** In panels (a) and (b), delayed interactions are preserved, whereas panels (c) and (d) represent alternative forms: instantaneous start times (c) and continuous intervals (d). Different community structures, displayed in colors, are evaluated using L-Modularity. Each structure is optimal with respect to Q_{MM} , Q_{JM} , or both. All evaluations use $\gamma = \omega = 1$. Panels (a) and (b) are derived from the same temporal network but differ in community assignment; the MM model favors (a) over (b) ($0.75 > 0.71$), whereas the JM model favors (b) over (a) ($0.65 > 0.60$). This figure highlights the impact of interaction models and longitudinal null models on temporal community detection.

dynamic communities in temporal networks. These communities correspond to so-called *time modules* [22], i.e., sub link streams that exhibit both temporal and topological coherence with respect to their contribution to the L-Modularity score. Formally, the optimization procedure produces time modules, which are then interpreted as dynamic communities.

5.3.1 LAGO For Simple Link Streams

LAGO builds upon the Louvain method [7] and incorporates ideas inspired by Infomap [98] and Leiden [49], together with components specifically designed for link streams. The method was introduced to optimize L-Modularity on simple instantaneous link streams. Without discussing all the details of the algorithm, we summarize here the key elements to understand the adaptations required to optimize the generalized L-Modularity.

LAGO is composed of a *core loop*, which proceeds in two alternating phases: i) time module reassignment and ii) aggregation. The reassignment concerns atomic elements called *active time nodes*, that play a role equivalent to nodes in the original Louvain. At each step, the algorithm performs a *local move*, in which the active time nodes test the interest of joining the community of one of their *neighbors in the link stream*. If the move is accepted, all time segments delimited by consecutive temporal neighbors involved in both the source and target communities are reassigned accordingly.

While the core loop remains unchanged, we detail here the changes required to the definition of active time nodes and neighborhoods in link streams. We also detail the changes required to the *variants* of LAGO introduced in the previous chapter. An illustration of the modified core loops can be found in Fig. 5.4 (timestamp-based) and Fig. 5.5 (interval-based).

5.3.2 LAGO for Generalized L-Modularity

In this section, we detail how LAGO can be adapted to optimize the generalized L-modularity introduced in Definition 5.3.

5.3.2.1 Active Time Nodes

In the original LAGO (see Chapter 4), we introduced the concept of *active time nodes*, that play the role of the atomic elements manipulated by the algorithm, equivalent to nodes in the static Louvain.

Definition 5.4. Let $L = (T, V, E)$ be a simple instantaneous link stream. The set \mathcal{A}

of **active time nodes** is defined as the set of node–time pairs involved in interactions:

$$\mathcal{A} = \{(u, t) \in V \times T \mid \exists v \in V \text{ such that } (u, v, t) \in E\} \quad (5.9)$$

In generalized LAGO, the definition of active time nodes must be modified to account for both incoming and outgoing timestamp-based interactions in:

Definition 5.5. Let $L = (T, V, E)$ be a general timestamp-based link stream. The set \mathcal{A} of **active time nodes** is defined as the set of node–time pairs involved in interactions:

$$\mathcal{A} = \{(u, t) \in V \times T \mid \exists v \in V, t' \in T \text{ such that } (u, v, t, t', \cdot) \in E \text{ or } (v, u, t', t, \cdot) \in E\}. \quad (5.10)$$

This definition also applies without modification to **weighted, delayed, and multipartite** interactions.

For **interval-based** interactions, the notion of active time nodes is no longer suitable. Instead, we introduce *active time-segment nodes*. In the continuous setting, the atomic elements manipulated by the algorithm must correspond to temporal units that can be uniquely assigned to a time module. Directly using interaction intervals as atomic elements is problematic because overlapping intervals cannot be unambiguously assigned to a single time module. To avoid this issue, we redefine the set of interval-based interactions by segmenting them so that no interaction starts or ends within any resulting segment. This ensures that the resulting segments form a partition of time where interaction boundaries are aligned. Formally, each interaction interval is *segmented* so that no other interaction starts or ends inside the resulting time segments. The resulting segments are then used to define the atomic elements manipulated by the algorithm, referred to as *active time-segment nodes*. Let

$$\mathcal{T} = \bigcup_{u, v, t_s, t_e \in E} \{t_s, t_e\}$$

be the set of all start and end times of interaction intervals, and let $\mathcal{S}([t_s, t_e])$ denote the partition of $[t_s, t_e)$ induced by \mathcal{T} , defined by $t_s = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{n+1} = t_e$, that is $\mathcal{S}([t_s, t_e]) = \{[t_i, t_{i+1})\}_{i=0}^n$. We denote

$$E_{\mathcal{S}} = \bigcup_{u, v, t_s, t_e \in E} \mathcal{S}([t_s, t_e])$$

the set of continuous interactions after *segmentation*. LAGO can then be applied on *active time-segment nodes*.

Definition 5.6. Let $L = (T, V, E)$ be a general link stream with interval-based inter-

actions. The set \mathcal{A}_S of **active time-segment nodes** is defined as the set of node–time-segment pairs involved in interactions:

$$\mathcal{A}_S = \{(u, [t_s, t_e]) \mid \exists v \in V \text{ such that } (u, v, t_s, t_e, \cdot) \in E_S \text{ or } (v, u, t_s, t_e, \cdot) \in E_S\}. \quad (5.11)$$

As illustrated in Figure 5.5 on an interval-based link stream, LAGO initially assigns each active time-segment node to its own time module, and then moves them between neighbor time modules. The move phase does not impact other active time-segment node affiliations since the segmented set of interval-based interactions prevents overlapping by design.

The *trimmed community property* demonstrated in [22], which justifies restricting the optimization of L-Modularity to active time nodes in the instantaneous setting, naturally extends to the continuous case when considering active time-segment nodes. Extending dynamic communities towards non active time segments lowers L-Modularity, analogously to the instantaneous case.

Note that considering E_S instead of E changes neither the weight of the network w , nor the weight of interactions $W_{uv \in C}$ from u to v within community C , nor the in or out degree $k_u^{\text{in}}, k_u^{\text{out}}$ of a node u . Only the number m of interactions is affected. LAGO is applied with the initial number of interactions m , computed before the segmentation phase.

5.3.2.2 Neighborhood in Link Streams

In the original LAGO, the notion of neighbors is redefined as a combination of temporal and topological neighbors, so that the algorithm tests extensions of communities in both modes. The definition is slightly adapted in the generalized case as follows:

Topological neighbors correspond, as in static networks, to nodes involved in the same interaction. In the directed setting, the direction of the interaction is ignored when defining neighbors, while for delayed interactions, the corresponding active time nodes may occur at different timestamps.

Temporal neighbors correspond to the previous and next active occurrences of the same node. For interval-based interactions, the same definition extends to active time-segment nodes.

The segmentation procedure introduced above ensures that, in the interval-based setting, interacting nodes share time segments of identical duration, which guarantees well-defined topological neighbors.

5.3.2.3 Local Moves

In LAGO, the *local move* procedure remains unchanged in the generalized setting. For interval-based interactions, the reassignment rule naturally extends to *active time-segment nodes*: when a move is accepted, all time segments delimited by consecutive temporal neighbors and involved in both the source and target communities are reassigned accordingly. Figures 5.4, 5.5 illustrate this mechanism for both timestamp-based and interval-based interactions.

Figure 5.4: **Example of LAGO application on a timestamp-based link stream.** Each *active time node* (black dots) initially belongs to its own time module. Then, in panel (a), each one (e.g., thick orange-circled) explores among its *neighbors* (thin orange-circled) the best move for reassignment. Once no move improves L-Modularity anymore, LAGO stops, yielding two dynamic communities in blue and green (panel b). The time segments between successive active time nodes are assigned to a community when both endpoints belong to the same community; otherwise they remain unassigned, highlighting transitions in node membership over time.

5.3.2.4 Variations

The original LAGO includes several variations. Among them, STNM and STEM require adaptation for interval-based interactions: they operate on active time-segment nodes instead of active time nodes, with the segmentation procedure ensuring that moves do not create inconsistencies with overlapping time intervals in time modules. All other variants, including fast exploration mode and RIR, remain directly applicable without modification.

5.4 Applications on Real-World Data

In this section, we illustrate the application of our contribution for dynamic community detection beyond simple temporal networks on real-world data. We demonstrate that LAGO successfully optimizes L-Modularity on those real-world datasets, and that the communities discovered provide reasonable insights. We illustrate results on weighted

Figure 5.5: **Example of LAGO application on an interval-based link stream.** The interval-based link stream (panel a) is first *segmented* so each *active time-segment node* (black rectangles) has at most one neighbor per node in time (panel b). Each active time-segment node initially belongs to its own time module. Then, in panel (c), each one (e.g., thick orange segment) explores among its *neighbors* (thin orange segments) the best move for reassignment. Once no move improves L-Modularity, LAGO stops, yielding two dynamic communities in blue and green (panel d).

and directed temporal networks in Section 5.4.1; interval-based and delayed interactions in Section 5.4.2; and bipartite temporal networks in Section 5.4.3. Table 5.1 summarizes core features of the mentioned networks.

Table 5.1: **Summary of the real-world temporal networks.** All datasets are preprocessed to reduce their volume and facilitate visualization. The table reports the main structural and temporal properties of each network after preprocessing. *# Active times* corresponds to the number of distinct time instants with at least one recorded interaction. *# Active time nodes* corresponds to the number of distinct time–node pairs (t, v) (or time-segment–node pairs for interval-based interactions) participating in at least one interaction (see Definitions 5.5, 5.6). Averages are computed over interactions.

	Eurovision 5.4.1				Citi Bike 5.4.2		Bluesky 5.4.3
	5.6a	5.6b	5.6c	5.6d	5.7a	5.7b	5.9
Duration	21 years				4 hours		9 months
# Nodes	49				46		283 + 259
# Active times	21				–	176	3 598
# Active time nodes	696				413	411	16 550
# Interactions	3 224	3 224	2 816	2 816	214		10 179
Total weight	8 487	–	8 487	–	–		–
Avg weight	2.63	–	3	–	–		–
Avg duration / delay	–	–	–	–	23 minutes		–
Instantaneous	x	x	x	x	–	–	x
Delayed	–	–	–	–	–	x	–
Interval-based	–	–	–	–	x	–	–
Weighted	x	–	x	–	–	–	–
Directed	x	x	–	–	–	–	–
Multipartite	–	–	–	–	–	–	x

5.4.1 A Voting Network: the Eurovision Song Contest

We apply LAGO to the voting network of the Eurovision Song Contest, an annual international music competition in which participating countries submit original songs. Under the pre-2016 voting scheme, each country assigns a single set of points (1–8, 10, and 12) to its top ten performances, based on an aggregation of jury and televote rankings.

Several studies have analyzed Eurovision data from a network perspective, highlighting voting biases that cannot be explained solely by song quality [106–109]. Without aiming to revisit these findings in depth, we model the data as a temporal network and apply LAGO to investigate whether such voting patterns naturally emerge.

The dataset¹ contains detailed voting records, including the voting country, the

¹<https://github.com/Spijkervet/eurovision-dataset/releases/tag/2023>

receiving country, the year, and the number of points awarded. These data naturally define a temporal, directed, and weighted network, where nodes represent countries and edges represent votes.

Country participation varies over time. To ensure consistency, we restrict the analysis to the period 1995–2015 and consider only votes cast during the final stage.

5.4.1.1 Preference Normalization

To isolate voting preferences beyond overall performance, following [109], we normalize votes as follows. For each year t , let

$$w_{ab}^{(t)} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{w}_b^{(t)}$$

respectively denote the number of points assigned by country a to country b , and the average number of points received by country b over all voting countries. We define the preference weight:

$$\tilde{w}_{ab}^{(t)} = w_{ab}^{(t)} - \bar{w}_b^{(t)}.$$

Only positive values are retained, i.e.,

$$\hat{w}_{ab}^{(t)} = \max(0, \tilde{w}_{ab}^{(t)}).$$

This transformation aims to remove the baseline effect of song performance and highlight relative voting affinities between countries. The resulting network is temporal, directed, and weighted, with edges encoding positive preference weights.

5.4.1.2 Network Variants

To assess the impact of modeling choices, we construct four network representations: (a) Directed / weighted: original normalized network; (b) Directed / unweighted: all nonzero weights set to 1; (c) Undirected / weighted: reciprocal edges are merged into a single undirected edge with weight ; (d) Undirected / unweighted: same as above, with all weights set to 1.

5.4.1.3 LAGO Configuration

LAGO is applied using the Mean Membership expectation, with parameters $\gamma = 4$ and $\omega = 4$. Since the defaults $\gamma = \omega = 1$ returned many small communities, we increase them in order to uncover structures relevant for visual analysis. STEM refinement is performed after each iteration of the core loop, and the fast exploration mode is enabled. For each configuration, the algorithm is run 10 times, and the partition with the highest L-Modularity is retained.

5.4.1.4 Results

The results are shown in Fig. 5.6. Countries are denoted using ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 codes. The bold codes in the figure correspond to countries commented in the following; for example, **es** (Spain), **pt** (Portugal), **cy** (Cyprus), **gr** (Greece), **se** (Sweden), and **no** (Norway).

(a) Directed / weighted. (b) Directed / un-weighted. (c) Undirected / weighted. (d) Undirected / un-weighted.

Figure 5.6: Temporal Eurovision voting network under four modeling configurations. Countries are shown on the y-axis (ISO 3166 codes) and years on the x-axis. Black squares indicate years in which a country participated in the vote. Edges are omitted for clarity. Colors represent dynamic communities detected by LAGO; only the 12 most present communities, corresponding to bold node labels, are shown in color, while all others are displayed in light grey. Comparing the four configurations highlights the impact of modeling choices (directed/undirected and weighted/unweighted) on the resulting community structure.

We observe substantial differences across the four configurations. These differences are not attributable to optimization variability, as multiple runs consistently converge to similar high-scoring solutions.

Several detected communities align with known voting patterns reported in prior work. In particular [106], the pairs (Spain, Portugal), (Cyprus, Greece), and (Sweden, Norway) are recurrently grouped together in the directed and weighted configuration.

In contrast, the unweighted representations fail to consistently recover some of these associations, notably the Sweden–Norway pair. This suggests that edge weights carry important information about the strength of voting preferences.

Finally, undirected representations tend to produce communities with shorter temporal persistence. This is consistent with the change in the L-Modularity formulation when directionality is removed: the degree product $k_u k_v$ replaces $k_u^{\text{out}} k_v^{\text{in}}$, which for asymmetric voting profiles reshapes the null expectation and makes sustained co-membership harder to justify statistically.

5.4.2 A Transportation System: Citi Bike

Transportation systems are commonly modeled as networks, where nodes represent locations and edges capture flows of people or goods [110–112], among others. Applying community detection methods to such data reveals underlying mobility structures and their potential evolution over time [113–115]. Link streams with delayed interactions are particularly well suited for modeling such temporal data. The goal here is not to provide a detailed analysis of transportation patterns, but rather to illustrate the relevance of our approach on real-world temporal network data.

In this section, we apply LAGO to bike trips between stations of the Citi Bike system, New York City’s public bicycle-sharing network. The dataset² provides station identifiers together with departure and arrival timestamps for each trip.

5.4.2.1 Modeling Choices

Trips can be modeled in two distinct ways. The most direct representation uses delayed interactions: each trip is an interaction starting at the departure time and ending at the arrival time, linking the origin and destination stations. Alternatively, trips can be modeled as continuous interactions, where the two stations are considered connected throughout the trip duration. This second representation assumes that stations are temporarily coupled while a bike is in transit, capturing ongoing system-level connectivity. In both cases, nodes correspond to stations and interactions correspond to trips. The objective is to show that generalized L-Modularity optimization is able to discover meaningful communities in these two formalisms directly with LAGO, and to show that the modeling choices indeed have an effect on the results.

The delayed link stream is constructed directly from the data, with each trip represented by a single delayed interaction. The continuous link stream is obtained by

²<https://s3.amazonaws.com/tripdata/index.html>

assigning to each trip a continuous interaction spanning its duration. In this case, each interaction is weighted by the inverse of its duration, ensuring that node degrees remain identical across the delayed and continuous representations. Consequently, for a fixed community structure, longitudinal expectations and the temporal penalty term are preserved. The only difference lies in how intra-community interaction weights are accumulated. This normalization ensures that L-Modularity values remain comparable across the two models, allowing for a meaningful comparison of the resulting dynamic communities.

We investigate how the choice between delayed and continuous interaction models affects the structure and stability of dynamic communities.

5.4.2.2 Data Filtering

We restrict the analysis to the time window from 6:30 to 11:30 on 2025-11-10 (Monday), corresponding to morning commuting hours when usage is structured and intense. Only trips lasting at least 15 minutes are retained. Stations with the lowest degrees are iteratively removed until fewer than 50 stations remain.

These filtering steps reduce noise, remove marginal nodes, and limit the size of the temporal network to enable visual inspection, while emphasizing delayed interactions by focusing on relatively long trips.

5.4.2.3 LAGO Configuration

LAGO is applied using the Mean Membership expectation. The parameters γ and ω are both set to the default value of 1. STEM refinement is performed after each iteration of the core loop, and the fast exploration mode is enabled. Each experiment is repeated 10 times, and the solution of highest L-Modularity is retained.

5.4.2.4 Results

Figure 5.7 presents the communities obtained under both models. The number of detected communities differs significantly (15 vs 7), highlighting the impact of the interaction model.

Continuous and delayed interaction models produce distinct temporal patterns in dynamic community structure. Continuous interactions reduce isolated time-node memberships and distribute the influence of interactions over their duration, resulting in smoother transitions between communities and more temporally coherent node assignments.

Delayed interactions emphasize temporally localized events, producing communities that can persist longer and allowing nodes to interleave across multiple dynamic communities. Under this model, some communities span nearly the entire lifespan of

(a) 15 communities detected using continuous interactions.

(b) 7 communities detected using delayed interactions.

Figure 5.7: **Citi Bike trips on the morning of 2025-11-10 under two link stream models.** Horizontal lines correspond to the nodes, i.e., docking stations. Colors indicate dynamic communities identified by LAGO. For clarity, only the 12 most present communities are colored; others are shown in light grey. Edges (trips) are displayed as delayed interactions for readability. Results differ between the two representations.

the network and include nodes that are not present simultaneously (e.g., yellow, red, and turquoise communities), while other nodes belong only briefly (e.g., node 6173.08, second from the bottom, which switches from turquoise to orange to blue and back to orange). Such patterns, enabled by delayed interactions, provide novel insight into fine-grained temporal variations in transportation behavior.

Overall, continuous interactions yield smoother, more coherent community structures, whereas delayed interactions result in finer, more fragmented communities that capture localized temporal dynamics. By systematically considering delayed interactions, it is possible to characterize temporal patterns that are not observable in conventional continuous models.

5.4.3 A Bipartite Network: Bluesky Messages

Online social networks can be modeled as temporal multipartite networks, where nodes represent heterogeneous entities (e.g., users and hashtags), and edges correspond to timestamped interactions. Community detection methods applied to such data reveal latent groups and the temporal evolution of topics or user interests [116–118]. However, many approaches rely on simplifying assumptions such as time aggregation or network projection, potentially obscuring temporal or structural information.

In this section, we model Bluesky messages as a bipartite link stream. Nodes correspond to users and hashtags, and interactions encode the publication of a hashtag by a user at a given time. We then apply LAGO to uncover dynamic communities. Our objective is illustrative: we aim to demonstrate the capacity of the method to directly handle this type of graph, rather than to provide an exhaustive social network analysis.

Bluesky is an online social network where users publish short messages that may include hashtags. Hashtags are user-defined keywords prefixed by the symbol $\#$. They act as explicit markers of content and facilitate topic-based organization. Because they directly reflect the intended topic of a message, they are well-suited for studying topic dynamics and community formation.

5.4.3.1 Modeling Choices

The dataset, introduced by Failla and Rossetti [119], was collected between February and May 2024 and comprises approximately 4 million users and 235 million posts.

We model the data as a bipartite temporal network by defining interactions of the form (u, v, t) , where a user u publishes a post containing the hashtag v at time t . By construction, interactions occur exclusively between users and hashtags, resulting in a bipartite structure, as illustrated in Fig. 5.8.

Applying LAGO to this network enables the identification of (i) groups of hashtags

co-used over time, revealing topic dynamics, and (ii) groups of users sharing coherent hashtag usage, capturing evolving user communities.

Figure 5.8: **Bluesky data representation.** Three users publish eight posts over time, involving nine distinct hashtags. Each post generates one or more interactions between the posting user and the hashtags it contains, all timestamped at the time of publication.

5.4.3.2 Data Filtering

We remove posts containing more than 10 hashtags, as they are likely to correspond to noise or spam. We then iteratively filter out users and hashtags with the lowest degrees. These filtering steps reduce noise, remove marginal nodes, and limit the size of the temporal network to improve interpretability.

5.4.3.3 LAGO Configuration

LAGO is applied using the Joint Membership expectation. Parameters are set to the default values $\gamma = 1$ and $\omega = 1$. STEM refinement is performed after each iteration of the core loop, and the fast exploration mode is enabled. The algorithm is run 10 times, and the solution with the highest L-Modularity is retained.

5.4.3.4 Results

Figure 5.9.a displays communities of hashtags over time. Each point corresponds to an occurrence of a hashtag in a message. We focus on two sets of semantically equivalent variants: (i) *UkrainianView*, *ukrainianview*, and *Ukrainianview*; and (ii) *FossilFriday* and *fossilfriday*.

One might expect such variants to belong to the same community. However, this is not systematically observed, suggesting heterogeneous usage across user groups.

(a) Temporal usage of 50 hashtags.

(b) Temporal activity of 158 users.

Figure 5.9: **Visualization of LAGO results on the Bluesky bipartite temporal network.** Black squares indicate activity—hashtag usage or user publication—at a given time. Colors represent dynamic communities detected by LAGO. Only communities associated with the bolded hashtags are colored, while all others are displayed in light gray. For readability, only subsets of users and hashtags most related to the highlighted communities are shown.

For group (i), the variants are distributed across three communities (light green, purple, and pink). The light green community appears early and dominates. The purple community emerges in the final quarter of the observation period, possibly as a restructuring of the former. The pink community is smaller and more isolated. Around early February 2024, a transition occurs: *ukrainianview* shifts to the pink community, while the remaining variants move from the light green to the purple community.

This transition is better understood from the user perspective: approximately one-third of the users in the light green community stop using these hashtags, while few new users adopt them.

For group (ii), multiple user communities engage with the same topic over time. Most exhibit high turnover (e.g., brown, light orange, purple, orange communities). In contrast, the blue community remains stable and predominantly uses *FossilFriday*, while others favor the lowercase form *fossilfriday*. The associated hashtags evolve over time, including *WomeninStem*, *Arachtober*, *paleontology*, and *climate*, whereas others such as *invertebrate* remain consistently present.

Chapter Summary

This chapter introduced a unified generalization of both L-Modularity and LAGO to weighted, directed, and multipartite interactions, as well as to instantaneous, continuous, and delayed temporal modalities. The central design principle is to avoid destructive transformations of the data: rather than projecting, aggregating, or otherwise simplifying the input before analysis, the framework operates directly on the raw interaction stream and encodes structural and temporal features explicitly in the quality function.

The applications on three real-world datasets confirm that LAGO successfully optimizes the generalized L-Modularity across diverse interaction types, producing communities that are interpretable in light of domain knowledge. More importantly, they illustrate that *modeling choices matter*: retaining edge weights and directions in the Eurovision network better recovers known voting blocs; choosing between delayed and continuous models on the Citi Bike data produces markedly different community structures; and the bipartite formulation on Bluesky captures joint user–hashtag dynamics that a unipartite projection would lose.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Perspectives

This thesis explored the problem of dynamic community detection at the exact time precision of the data, and investigated whether a Modularity-and-Louvain-style approach could be designed in that setting. The three contributions presented in Chapters 3–5 provide, taken together, a constructive answer. We close the manuscript by revisiting what these contributions establish and the directions they open.

6.1 Summary of Contributions

The three research questions formulated in Section 1.3 have each been addressed by a distinct methodological contribution.

6.1.0.1 RQ1 — Quality function.

Chapter 3 introduced *Longitudinal Modularity* (L-Modularity), a generalization of Newman’s Modularity [6] to temporal networks expressed as link streams [14]. The construction operates without prior aggregation of the data: communities can be short-lived or long-lived, and nodes can join or leave them at any moment of the timeline. We showed that L-Modularity reduces to classical Modularity in the static limit and that multilayer Modularity [17] can be recovered as a particular discretization of it, thereby positioning L-Modularity as a generalization of the two most widely used modularity-based formulations. We further established that the quality function satisfies a set of structural properties expected from a temporal community criterion. The contribution is detailed in [21].

6.1.0.2 RQ2 — Optimization algorithm.

Chapter 4 introduced *LAGO* (Longitudinal Agglomerative Greedy Optimization), an algorithm that optimizes L-Modularity directly on link streams. To the best of our knowledge, LAGO is the first method for dynamic community detection to operate at

the exact time precision of the data: it requires no prior time discretization, and the exact moments at which nodes enter or leave communities are themselves outputs of the algorithm rather than parameters of the analysis. LAGO transposes the agglomerative logic of Louvain [7] to the exact-time setting, and its modular design accommodates several greedy exploration strategies. The comparative analysis of fourteen algorithmic variants reported in Chapter 4 delineates the influence of individual design choices and suggests practical guidelines for selecting strategies in light of given optimization goals [22]. Beyond its immediate purpose, LAGO is applicable to any quality function over link streams sharing a design similar to L-Modularity.

6.1.0.3 RQ3 — Generality.

Chapter 5 lifted the simplifying assumption, adopted in C1 and C2, that interactions are simple, instantaneous, and unipartite. Building on existing extensions of the link stream formalism to weighted, directed, and bipartite cases [76], we proposed a *generalized link stream* model that natively supports weighted, directed, and multipartite interactions in combination with the three temporal modalities — instantaneous, continuous, and delayed — identified in Section 1.2. L-Modularity and LAGO were extended to this generalized setting in such a way that the original formulations are recovered as special cases. The validation on three real-world datasets — a directed and weighted voting network (Eurovision), a transportation network with delayed and continuous interactions (Citi Bike), and a bipartite social network (Bluesky) — shows that the framework produces domain-interpretable communities across this entire range of features, and that *modeling choices matter*: the type of interaction one chooses to model substantially changes which communities are detected, and the framework makes this choice explicit and reversible.

Taken together, C1, C2, and C3 form a single methodological pipeline — from quality function, to optimization algorithm, to general modeling framework — that, to the best of our knowledge, constitutes the first dynamic community detection approach combining exact time precision with broad support for the diversity of real-world temporal interactions.

6.2 Limitations and Perspectives

The framework is, of course, neither complete nor uniformly satisfactory. We discuss its main limitations together with the research directions they suggest.

Parameter selection and the temporal resolution limit. The generalized L-Modularity introduces two parameters that jointly control community granularity and

temporal stability: a resolution parameter γ , inherited from the static case, and a temporal-coupling parameter ω that controls how strongly the quality function penalizes community switches across time. While Chapter 5 reports empirically reasonable ranges and shows that the produced partitions vary smoothly with these parameters, a principled selection strategy is still lacking. The difficulty is compounded by the well-known resolution limit of static Modularity [50]: we conjecture that L-Modularity is affected by an analogous phenomenon in temporal form — communities too short in duration relative to the total temporal mass of the link stream may be invisible to the quality function — and that the two parameters interact with this limit in ways that warrant theoretical analysis. A systematic study, ideally yielding interpretable defaults, is the most pressing methodological follow-up.

Segmentation, scaling, and streaming. Three computational aspects of the framework warrant further investigation. The handling of continuous interactions in Chapter 5 relies on a segmentation step that partitions the timeline into atomic intervals, the number of which can grow rapidly when many overlapping continuous interactions are present. The current implementation remains tractable on the datasets considered, but its cost depends on the temporal density of the data rather than on its sheer volume, and a worst case combining many overlapping continuous interactions could become prohibitive. Capping the number of atomic intervals — at the price of merging interactions that are strictly distinct in time — would decouple runtime from this density and is worth exploring.

More generally, scalability remains a limitation of LAGO when applied to massive temporal networks: the datasets considered in this thesis, while diverse, are orders of magnitude smaller than the largest temporal networks one might encounter in practice, and the behavior of LAGO at that scale has not been systematically evaluated. We expect a practical limit beyond which the exact agglomerative procedure becomes prohibitive, and pushing beyond it will likely require to introduce variants allowing approximations of the quality function — sampling-based moves, sparsification of candidate operations, or parallelization of the local updates — designed to preserve community quality while accommodating the scale of the data.

On a different axis, LAGO is currently an algorithm applied in a retrospective way, after the complete collection of the data. Many systems for which the framework is most relevant — online platforms, sensor networks, transportation systems — are instead naturally streaming, and adapting LAGO so that the partition is updated incrementally as new interactions arrive would substantially broaden its operational reach. The local nature of the agglomerative updates is an asset in this respect.

Null model and temporal heterogeneity. The null model used throughout this work assumes interactions to be, in expectation, uniformly distributed over the timeline. Real-world temporal interactions are typically neither uniform nor stationary — human communications are bursty, urban transportation follows circadian patterns, online platforms exhibit weekly seasonalities. A null model insensitive to these regularities will, by construction, attribute part of the temporal heterogeneity of the data to the community structure when it merely reflects predictable rhythms of the underlying system. Designing temporally heterogeneous null models that remain compatible with the agglomerative core of LAGO is a well-defined research target. The temporal penalty itself raises a related question: in its current form it treats all community switches identically, regardless of the weight or salience of the surrounding interactions, and a more discriminating penalty would likely produce more faithful temporal partitions.

Beyond L-Modularity. Although the contributions of this thesis focus on an adaptation of modularity, the principles underlying the adaptation of this quality function into a link-stream compatible one are generic, being based on simple principles such as counting internal interactions or defining a temporal penalty for smoothness. Transposing the Map Equation [98] to link streams in the same spirit would yield a flow-based counterpart of L-Modularity, potentially solving some of its limits. New versions of SBM on link streams could also be defined, not centered on modeling evolutions with markov process, but rather like our L-Modularity, to discover exceptionally dense substreams.

Richer structural features, software, and applications. Several features routinely present in real datasets are not yet covered. Signed interactions, in which positive and negative relations co-occur on the same timeline, are a natural extension of practical interest in political, ecological, and social networks. Higher-order interactions, in which several nodes participate jointly in a single event, would bring the framework closer to hypergraph-based representations. Overlapping communities, finally, would relax the strict partition assumption that L-Modularity inherits from Newman’s Modularity. Beyond these methodological extensions, the practical reach of the framework will depend on the maturity of its software implementation. An implementation of L-Modularity and LAGO is available¹ and was used for all experiments reported in this thesis; consolidating it is a natural next step. A substantial part of the success of static Modularity and Louvain [7] comes from their availability in standard libraries, and a comparable level of integration would be the most direct route by which the contributions of this thesis can become useful to practitioners across application domains.

¹https://github.com/fondationsahar/dynamic_community_detection

6.3 Closing Remarks

This thesis offers a single quality function, a single optimization algorithm, and a single modeling framework that together support, on temporal data, the kinds of community analyses that practitioners routinely perform on static networks. In its present form, the framework already covers a wide spectrum of practical settings, and the perspectives outlined above represent natural extensions of — rather than prerequisites for — its applied use. We hope that the methodological position it embodies — that the analysis of temporal networks should operate at the time precision at which the data was recorded, on the data as it was recorded — will prove useful well beyond the specific contributions of this thesis.

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